

BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

Deliverable 2.1

Regional case studies

Cyprus

Czech Republic

France

Greece

Portugal

Italy

Slovenia

Spain

Türkyie

BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

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Contents

1	Executive summary.....	8
2	Introduction.....	9
2.1	Objectives of BioINSouth.....	9
2.2	Objective of WP2	9
2.3	Objectives of Task 2.2. and the MARGs Kick Off Meetings (KOMs).....	9
3	BioINSouth MultiActor Regional Groups (MARGs).....	10
3.1	BioINSouth channels for the MARGs communication.....	13
4	Scenarios of Growth Definition	14
5	MARG KOMs methodology	15
5.1	Main recommendations and support info	16
5.1.1	Official event title.....	16
5.1.2	Objective.....	16
5.1.3	Agenda.....	16
5.2	Content preparation	17
5.2.1	Regional case study - Interviews information	17
5.2.2	HUB establishment working plan	17
5.3	Registration and venue	19
5.4	Required equipment, support material, logistics	19
5.5	Attendees	20
5.6	Mail to be sent after the event	20
5.7	Satisfaction survey	21
6	MARG KOMs organization and results	23
6.1	Andalusian MARG KOM.....	23
6.1.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	23
6.1.2	MARG KOM Results	27
6.2	Asturias MARG KOM.....	38
6.2.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	38
6.2.2	MARG KOM Results	42
6.3	Campania MARG KOM	50
6.3.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	50
6.3.2	MARG KOM Results	53
6.4	Centro Region/Portugal MARG KOM.....	62
6.4.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	62
6.4.2	MARG KOM Results	64

6.5	CYPRUS MARG KOM.....	77
6.5.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	77
6.5.2	MARG KOM Results	80
6.6	Nouvelle Aquitaine MARG KOM	90
6.6.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	90
6.6.2	MARG KOM Results	93
6.7	Peloponnese MARG KOM.....	97
6.7.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	97
6.7.2	MARG KOM Results	99
6.8	Slovenia MARG KOM	112
6.8.1	MARG KOM Organization Phase	112
6.8.2	MARG KOM Results	117
7	CONCLUSIONS	129
	Annex I: Terms of Reference for the Multi-Actor Regional Groups of BioINSouth Template	134
	Annex II: Declaration of Acceptance (DoA) Template	144
	Annex III: Email Invitation Template	145
	Annex IV: Interview Script and Consent Form template.....	146
	Annex V: Andalusian MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.....	152
	Annex VI : Asturias MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.....	182
	Annex VII: Campania MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.	204
	Annex VIII: Centro Region MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.....	232
	Annex IX: Cyprus MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.	254
	Annex X: Nouvelle Aquitaine MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.	272
	Annex XI: Peloponnese MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.....	280
	Annex XII: Slovenia MARG KOM. Reporting Documents.	284

Tables

Table 1: Composition of BioINSouth MARGs in M6 (November 2024).....	12
Table 2: Total interviews per region and type of profile.....	15
Table 3: MARG Andalucía members interviewed.	29
Table 4: Workplan for the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía.....	32
Table 5: List of participants registered to Asturias MARG KoM event.	42
Table 6: List of attendees to Asturias MARG KoM.	43
Table 7: List of registrations to Campania MARG KoM.....	52
Table 8: List of attendees to Campania MARG KoM.....	53
Table 9: Working plan for the BioINSouth Campania HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members.	57
Table 10: List of participants registered to Centro Region MARG KoM event.....	64
Table 11: List of attendees to Centro Region MARG KoM.....	65
Table 12: MARG Centro Region members interviewed.....	67
Table 13: Workplan for the BioINSouth HUB Centro Region - PT.....	69
Table 14: Cyprus MARG KOM Registrations.....	80
Table 15: Working plan for the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members.	85
Table 16: Peloponnese MARG KOM Registrations.....	98
Table 17: Peloponnese MARG KOM Participants.....	99
Table 18: Working plan for the BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members.....	104
Table 19: Slovenia MARG KOM Registrations.....	116
Table 20: Slovenia MARG KOM Participants.....	118
Table 21: MARG Slovenia members interviewed.	121
Table 22: HUB activities for 2025, discussed during the workshop.....	122
Table 23: KPIs by Region: Registration, Attendance and Stakeholder Composition.....	132

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Monitoring of the BioINSouth official LinkedIn page followers and engagement rate for the period November 2024-April 2025.....	13
Figure 2: HUB establishment working plan Template.....	18
Figure 3: Andalusia KOM: Event creative used for social media.....	23
Figure 4: Andalusia KOM: Agenda of the event.....	24
Figure 5: Andalusia KOM: Photos taken during the BioINSouth event at TRANSFIERE.	25
Figure 6: BioINSouth Andalucía Shared Folder.....	26
Figure 7: María García [CTA] presenting BioINSouth project. The BioINSouth Context.....	28
Figure 8: María García [CTA] presenting (A) the members of the MARG Andalucía and (B) the workplan for the creation of the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía.....	29
Figure 9: MARG members participating in the open discussion on the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía Work Plan.....	31
Figure 10: Quality Assessment Questionnaire for the BioINSouth MARG KOM.....	37
Figure 11: BioINSouth presentation to AGROOE consortium members by Cristina Viera (ASINCAR).....	39
Figure 12: Asturias MARG KoM agenda.....	40

Figure 13: Photos obtained during Asturias MARG KOM were attendees, site distributions and resources used are observed.....	41
Figure 14: Introduction and presentation of the session information.....	45
Figure 15: Slide to promote the discussion (including the results of the discussion).....	45
Figure 16: Asturias’s HUB mission and vision.....	46
Figure 17: Asturias’s HUB use cases.....	47
Figure 18: Asturias’s HUB implementation plan.....	48
Figure 19: Presentation to MARG members on the BioINSouth project and the main objectives of the Kick-Off Meeting.....	51
Figure 20: Discussion with Valeria Fascione (Regional Assessor - Research, Innovation and Start up, Italian Region Campania) regarding the HUB and its implementation.....	51
Figure 21: Campania MARG members during the kick-off meeting.....	51
Figure 22: Photo taken during the BioINSouth event at Biocant Park.....	63
Figure 23: Photo taken at the end of the BioINSouth event at Biocant Park prior to the networking lunch.....	63
Figure 24: Carlos Magalhães e Silva [P-BIO] presenting BioINSouth project and the BioINSouth Context.....	66
Figure 25: Centro Region MARG KOM Satisfaction Survey Results.....	76
Figure 26: a) Event venue, b) Presentation and discussion during event with MARGs members, c) Outdoor area of event venue used for networking, d) Pre-meeting discussions.....	78
Figure 27: a) Frederick University’s pads & pens, b) Frederick University’s brochure, c) Large screen for BioINSouth banner, d) Laptop and large screen for presentation.....	79
Figure 28: Presentation and Discussion Sessions.....	82
Figure 29: Diagram used in Miro to guide the interactive/ discussion session.....	82
Figure 30: Presentation of the regional/national case study analysis.....	83
Image 31: Workshop evaluation based on satisfaction survey.....	89
Figure 32: Meeting room of the MARG KOM.....	91
Image 33: Official photo of MARG members presents at the KOM. *.....	91
Image 34: Regional stakeholder mapping workshop.....	95
Image 35: Overview of the mapping.....	95
Figure 36: Presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives.....	100
Figure 37: Part of the presentation of Nasos Makios (KLIMIS) (left) and the platform of the Clube presented by Dr. Y. Fallas (right).....	101
Figure 38: Part of the presentation of Maria Andriellou (GBC) (left) and the INDBioCAT project presented by Prof. Dr. E. Topakas (NTU) (right).....	101
Figure 39: Part of the presentation of Nikos Damatis (Hellabiom) (left) and the activities of the Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU) presented by Prof. Dr. F. Ververidis (HMU) (right).....	101
Figure 40: Presentation of the Business Plan of the AIM-HQ OIL project (left) and the Joint European master’s degree (AIM-OPTIMOIL) between HMU-GR, ES-UJAEN and IT-UNIBAS, both presented by Prof. Dr. F. Ververidis (HMU) (right).....	102
Figure 41: The picture of the attendees. 16 belong to the MARGs, 3 are from the organizing committee and 1 was an external invited Master student from the International Hellenic University.....	110
Figure 42: Promotional poster for the event Bio(r)evolution: Where to Direct the National Bioeconomy?.....	112
Figure 43: Slovenia MARG KOM Agenda.....	113
Figure 44: Highlights of the event, project presentations, and audience participation.....	115
Figure 45: Brainstorming session.....	115

Figure 46: Alenka Dovč presenting BioINSouth project, MARG members and tasks.....	120
Figure 47: Participants filling out an online survey regarding area of focus of Slovenian bioeconomy HUB.....	121
Figure 48: Registrations vs. Attendance by Region.....	132
Figure 49: Stakeholder Composition by Region	133

ABBREVIATIONS

CTA	Technological Corporation of Andalusia
DDGS	Distillers Dried Grains with Solubles
DoA	Declaration of Acceptance
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
MARG	Multi-Actor Regional Groups
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-governmental organisations
QH	Quadruple Helix
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SH	Stakeholder
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
ToR	Terms of Reference
TRLs	Technology Readiness Levels

1 Executive summary

Deliverable D2.1 "Regional Case Studies" provides a comprehensive account of the activities conducted within Task 2.1. "Set up of Quadruple Helix Multi-Actor Regional Groups" and Task 2.2 "Organization of the multi-actor approach in case study regions" as part of Work Package 2 "Development of the BioINSouth multi-actor approach framework" aiming at establishing and initiating the project's multi-actor framework at the regional level, a prerequisite for achieving BioINSouth's goal of integrating ecological limits into bioeconomy strategies across Southern European regions.

The work documented in D2.1 focused on the practical organization of regional actors, particularly the Multi-Actor Regional Groups (MARGs), to facilitate their crucial role in co-creation and co-validation activities. These groups, designed to represent the quadruple helix (policymakers, industry, academia, civil society), were formed with a total of **92 members** across the eight pilot regions, reflecting gender balance with **43% female participation**. The MARGs are positioned as the project's regional advisory bodies, tasked with providing strategic input and aligning project outcomes with regional needs and contexts.

A central activity was the organization and execution of the MARG Kick-Off Meetings (KOMs) in each of the eight regions during March 2025. These KOMs served as the official launch of MARG activities and had the multi-faceted purpose of introducing the BioINSouth project, presenting the MARGs' role, validating preliminary regional findings derived from initial interviews, and, crucially, initiating the co-creation of a regional working plan for the establishment of the local BioINSouth HUB. Preparation included conducting **35 semi-structured** interviews with MARG members across regions to gather initial regional insights to build the regional case studies.

The KOMs successfully mobilised a total of **140 stakeholders registered** and **120 attended**, yielding an exceptional attendance rate of approximately **86 %**. **Gender balance was nearly achieved (48 % men, 52 % women)**, and stakeholder representation across the quadruple-helix was **academia (43%), private sector (31%), public administration (17%), and civil society (10%)**. Discussions at the KOMs provided valuable insights into the diverse regional bioeconomy landscapes, highlighting common barriers such as regulatory hurdles, economic/financing constraints, and knowledge gaps, as well as regional-specific challenges and opportunities.

Key outcomes of the activity include the completion of a **Regional Report and a Regional HUB Working Plan** for each of the eight case study regions. The successful organization of all eight KOMs within the designated timeframe, as measured by key performance indicators (KPIs) related to attendance, MARG member participation, and deliverable completion, demonstrates the effective implementation of this phase.

In summary, **Deliverable D2.1** has successfully established the foundational multi-actor framework and initiated regional engagement through the MARGs and their KOMs. The insights gathered and the regional documents produced (Regional Reports and Working Plans) provide essential, validated input tailored to each region. This work constitutes a critical basis for the subsequent development and operationalisation of the regional HUBs (WP3) and will inform other future project activities, ensuring that BioINSouth's strategies are grounded in the specific realities and needs of the Southern European regions.

2 Introduction

2.1 Objectives of BioINSouth

The BioINSouth project aims to assist decision makers in southern European regions with integrating ecological limits into their bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps. Through the development of guidelines and digital tools, the project seeks to foster circular bio-based activities while minimising environmental impact.

BioINSouth targets to enhance regional competitiveness and innovation in the bio-based sectors of Southern Mediterranean European regions. By establishing regional HUBs in eight European regions (Campania - Italy, Andalusia and Asturias - Spain, Centro - Portugal, Nouvelle-Aquitaine - France, Peloponnese - Greece, Cyprus and Slovenia) and engaging a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, public authorities, SMEs, and civil society, collaboration and data sharing are fostered through Multi-Actor Regional Groups (MARGs).

The HUBs will facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange, thereby enhancing regional competitiveness and innovation while also contributing to the EU's fair and green transition. Valuable know-how on the creation of the HUBs and the registration of policies, as well as insights to aid replication will be available through additional cooperation with Czech Republic (BIO EAST HUB), Turkey, and Argentina through the Advisory Committee, to create replicable models for sustainable bioeconomy development in southern Europe.

2.2 Objective of WP2

BioINSouth WP2 “Development of the BioINSouth multi-actor approach framework “aimed at shaping and building the project multi-actor framework following a two-fold approach:

- (1) by setting up stable quadruple helix MultiActor Regional Groups, acting as core group and ‘seeds’ of each future regional BioINSouth HUBs in southern European countries, that will support the partners along the project duration with data, information and active participation in interviews and co-creation workshops in the development of the activities performed by BioINSouth,
- (2) by mapping and engaging relevant stakeholders (civil society with special focus on NGOs, public authorities, regional research support agencies, farmers and farmers’ associations, market operators, in particular SMEs, RTOs) in the regions of interest, as a wider supporting element for the generation and obtention of relevant technical and knowledge basis for the ‘multi-actor approach’.

2.3 Objectives of Task 2.2. and the MARGs Kick Off Meetings (KOMs)

BioINSouth T2.2. “Organization of the multi-actor approach in case study regions” (M6-M12) is focused in organising the various actors and stakeholders in each region (namely the MARG members) into a well-organized case-study region, in order to effectively ease their co-creation and co-validation activities and efforts through the workshops and events planned in the project workplan.

As a first step for building the case study, 4 of the MARG members in each region have given semi-structured interviews region with questions aiming at defining scenarios of growth for the BioINSouth HUBs, as a source of information for the activities to be developed under WP4.

The core activity of the task was the ideation, planning and organization of the MARG kick-off meetings in each of the BioINSouth regions, as the official launch of the MARG activities, following a multiple purpose:

- (i) meet and greet the participants;
- (ii) introduce the BioINSouth project, its objectives and the general project working plan for the next years;
- (iii) develop a regional MARG working plan for the implementation of the BioINSouth HUB in the region/country;
- (iv) present and validate the results on the regional scenarios of growth from the interviews.

The main results on the regional analysis of the case study, as well as each MARG working plan for the implementation of the BioINSouth regional/national HUBs are included in this deliverable.

3 BioINSouth MultiActor Regional Groups (MARGs)

The BioINSouth project is solidly based on the multi-actor approach, as a way for gaining a deeper understanding of its eight regional complex systems and for developing more holistic and inclusive strategies to address the project's various challenges, recognizing the importance of considering diverse perspectives and acknowledging the role of different actors in shaping outcomes. The key elements of BioINSouth multi-actor approach methodology will be inherent to all the project development.

Considering this, the very first step towards the creation of this multi-actor framework within BioINSouth was the development of the MultiActor Regional Groups (hereinafter MARGs), consisting of representatives of at least eight relevant quadruple helix stakeholders per region, targeting local governments, business community, academic institutions, private sector and civil society (at least one from each category) linked to the bioeconomy sector.

The MARGs will be actively engaged throughout and beyond the lifespan of the project and can be considered the first step for the HUBs establishment at regional level in WP3.

The BioINSouth MARG Members can be considered the project's regional advisory body, offering knowledge and strategic direction to the BioINSouth Hubs Coordinators, in order to match the BioINSouth results with the requirements of the project's stakeholders and regions.

Throughout the project's duration and after, the MARGs will actively participate in co-creating, co-implementing, and co-monitoring meaningful HUBs models in the area.

More specifically, the BioINSouth MARG members contribute within the BioINSouth project by:

- encouraging collaboration;

- support the overall project stakeholder's analysis to map regional and local stakeholders' groups and development of a stakeholders' engagement strategy, enhancing their potential future involvement in the BioINSouth HUBs;
- participating in co-creative and co-validation sessions for the regional BioINSouth HUBs creation, overcoming barriers and seizing opportunities for circular bioeconomy at regional level;
- supporting the set-up and implementation of the BioINSouth HUBs network according to each MARG member interest and availability (i.e. attending events, participating in best practices exchange, etc);
- providing feedback and expertise on the environmental impact assessment and circularity monitoring system to be developed in the BioINSouth project, supporting its implementation in the BioINSouth regions;
- supporting the benchmarking process of the industries that have developed the most sustainable, efficient, and innovative bio-based chemical manufacturing processes, based on each MARG member knowledge about best practices in their own region;
- participating in the development of policy recommendations for sustainability and circularity in industrial bio-based systems.

For the setting up of BioINSouth MARGs, some materials were developed by CTA (Technological Corporation of Andalusia) and provided to the partners in charge of building these groups, namely:

- Terms of Reference (ToR): a short guide describing the BioINSouth project, the consortium partners, the MARGs' concept, its role, its expected contribution within the project implementation, as well as the benefits from the participation in it. See [Annex I](#).
- Declaration of Acceptance (DoA): a letter template to be filled in and signed by each expert for formalizing the adhesion to the regional MARG. See [Annex II](#).
- An email template for inviting regional experts to join the MARGs. See [Annex III](#).

Although the regional MARGs were officially set up by month 6 (November 2024), the potential inclusion of new members is open during the whole development of the project, enriching and enlarging the original core group.

At month 6, the 8 regional MARGs were established, with a total of **92 members**, from which **40 women** (43% of the total) ([Table 1](#)).

Table 1: Composition of BioINSouth MARGs in M6 (November 2024)

SH Category	Andalucía	Asturias	Campania	Centro Region	Cyprus	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	Peloponnese	Slovenia	TOTAL
Local governments	3	2	2	2	3	3	1	1	17
Academic institutions	6	3	6	2	3	4	5	3	32
Private sector	3	2	2	3	3	4	9	3	29
Civil society	1	1	2	1	1	2	4	2	14
TOTAL	13	8	12	8	10	13	19	9	92
TOTAL FEMALES	6	6	6	4	2	4	9	3	40

3.1 BioINSouth channels for the MARGs communication

The MARGs creation under WP2, as described in the previous sections, is a pillar on the establishment of the HUBs in following phases of the project. In terms of communication, their kick-off represents one of the first hallmarks of visibility for the BioINSouth project and its WP2 objectives to a wider specialised audience.

Under this context and in close interaction with WP7, the MARG KOM meetings were communicated in two levels, through:

- the channels of the MARGs coordinators
- the official BioINSouth channels (website and LinkedIn), through reposts of the participants' original posts

The role and context of the MARGs was communicated through the BioINSouth channels early on in the implementation phase, with graphic online material (M4 [Link](#)), while the communication of the MARGs KOMs taking place approximately in mid-March 2025 (M9) provided a boost on the followers of the BioINSouth LinkedIn page (currently more than 630 followers), and the engagement rate, as seen in the figures below.

Figure 1: Monitoring of the BioINSouth official LinkedIn page followers and engagement rate for the period November 2024-April 2025

The communication activities dedicated to MARGs are described in the F&T portal along with respective KPIs, while dedicated campaigns to meet the MARGs' experts are underway.

4 Scenarios of Growth Definition

As previously stated, the implementation of task 2.2 started with the design and performance of semi-structured interviews to MARG members (a minimum of 4 in each region) aiming at gathering relevant information from the regional stakeholder regarding each territory situation, to use it as backbone information for:

- (i) building the regional case studies for the HUBs design and implementation and
- (ii) define the scenarios of growth under task 4.1 “Design of an environmental impact assessment and circularity monitoring system for the southern European bioeconomy sector”, to identify the most significant biorefineries industries and other public or private entities that are involved in the value chain in the South of Europe.

For this purpose, an interview script was developed by Leitac (WP4 leader), with specific sections addressed to two main types of interviewee profile: technical and non-technical ones, giving the alternative to each BioINSouth Coordinator HUB to decide which section to use depending on the interviewee profile.

- SECTION A) For interviewee with technical profile
- SECTION B) For interviewee without technical profile,

A consent form to be signed by the interviewees was also performed. Its signature was compulsory.

Additionally, and based on the MARGs members database in each region, a preselection of the most interesting profiles per region to be interviewed was made by Leitac (as WP4 leader).

Although the interviews could be performed in local language, each interview produced a dedicated report in English based on the sections (A or B) structures.

The Interview Script and Consent Form template is available as [Annex IV](#).

A total of **35 interviews** were conducted under this task:

- 21 to technical profiles
- 14 to non-technical profiles

As per the gender balance of the action, 17 of the interviewees were women, a **49% of the total**.

The total interviews per region and type of profile can be found in the following table ([Table 2](#)).

The information retrieved during the interviews in each BioINSouth region was used as part of the MARGs KOM content and can be consulted from [Annex V](#) to [Annex XII](#) (Regional Reports).

Table 2: Total interviews per region and type of profile.

	Section A	Section B	Total	Men	Women
Andalusia	2	2	4	3	1
Asturias	2	2	4	1	3
Campania	2	2	4	2	2
Centro Region	2	2	4	2	2
Cyprus	2	2	4	2	2
Nouvelle-Aquitaine	4	0	4	3	1
Peloponnese	4	3	7	2	5
Slovenia	3	1	4	3	1
TOTAL	21	14	35	18	17

5 MARG KOMs methodology

As part of CTA's work package and task leadership, a document was prepared to guide each BioINSouth regional HUB coordinator on how to organise the Multi Actor Regional Groups (hereinafter MARGs) Kick-Off Meetings that need to be conducted in the frame of T2.2.

These MARGs KOM main objectives are:

- Introduce the BioINSouth project to the MARGs members and other relevant stakeholders.
- To conduct co-creation activities to develop a HUB development working plan, according to the guidelines developed in WP3;
- Present and validate the results on the regional scenario of growth, obtained from the questionnaires and 4 semi-structured interviews to regional MARG members, developed by WP4 leader.

According to the task description from the Description of Action (DoA), the following aspects need to be considered:

- Each BioINSouth regional HUB coordinator has to organise 1 MARG KOM event (preferably face-to-face) involving MARG members and other quadruple-helix actors. This needed to be done before 31st March 2025.
- With all the information obtained, each region had to draft its specific MARG working plan according to the HUB establishment guidelines provided by WP3. This reporting exercise needed to be done before 25th April 2025¹.

Other relevant considerations:

- It was possible to be flexible in the format of the event according to the context and situation of each host and the corresponding region.

¹ Report template provided by CTA.

- Each BioINSouth regional HUB coordinator was responsible for formatting the agenda, inviting attendees, disseminating the event and taking care of the registration process and satisfaction survey feedback gathering.
- Regarding communication activities of the event, each partner should have taken the lead on this. BioINSouth social media channels could support the events dissemination, when possible, in coordination with PNO.

5.1 Main recommendations and support info

This section presents the main recommendations to be considered for each event's further shaping and definition.

5.1.1 Official event title

The title would include « BioINSouth Project – [REGION/COUNTRY NAME] Multi Actor Regional Group Kick Off Meeting ». HUBs coordinators can add any additional subtitle if desired/needed.

5.1.2 Objective

The following objectives were expected from the MARGs KOM:

1. To spread the word about BioINSouth main aims, activities and timeline,
2. To present the MARG objectives, members and roles within the project (for additional information about this you can check the Terms of Reference for MARG members);
3. To share some preliminary results at regional/national level from the questionnaires answers,
4. To co-design a working plan for the HUB design and implementation
5. To gather other potentially relevant information and feedback that could be used in the subsequent project activities.

5.1.3 Agenda

According to the DoA, the agenda should include the following sections:

- Meet and greet the participants,
- Introducing the BioINSouth project, its objectives and the general working plan,
- Develop the specific MARG working plan according to the BioINSouth one developed in WP3 and
- Present and validate the results on the regional scenarios of growth from the questionnaires and interviews.

An example of a tentative agenda is provided below. This could be slightly adapted to the format of the event (preferably face-to-face one) and also the region/country and regional/national HUB coordinator needs.

1. Coffee or cocktail networking // Attendees connection (depending on the meeting time)
2. Introduction session: welcome attendants, brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop
3. Presentation of the regional/national case study analysis preliminary results from the questionnaires answers, and possible discussion about them with MARG members not

interviewed (some support tools can be used to show the results and dynamize a short discussion about them (as PPT, mentimeter, etc.)

4. Explanation of the MARG structure concept, objectives, members and roles within the project
5. Presentation of the HUBs concept and main guidelines (from WP3's results)
6. Co-creation of a working plan for the HUB design and implementation at regional/national level, during the BioINSouth project's duration.
7. Wrap-up session and information about next steps.
8. Lunch or cocktail networking (depending on the meeting time)

The event could be done in local language (preferred) or in English. For the project presentation, the one prepared by the project communication leader (PNO), as well as any other D&C relevant material can be used.

5.2 Content preparation

5.2.1 Regional case study - Interviews information

Each HUB coordinator is in charge of analyse and elaborate the information regarding the case study based on its regional interviews' answers. During the presentation of the regional interviews results, the HUB coordinators can check with the MARG members the accuracy of this information and gather additional one from MARG members not previously interviewed.

WP4 leader (Leitat) provided some preliminary results from the general interviews analysis to each HUB coordinator, to complement the regional vision.

5.2.2 HUB establishment working plan

As a result of the MARG KOM, a working plan towards the establishment of the HUB was developed together with the MARG members following the template included below ([Figure 2](#)):

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE		Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese								
N°	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTI	KEY REGIONAL PARTNER	RESOURCE NEEDED	TIME FRAM	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping									
2	Regional needs assessment									
3	Analysis of pilot case studies									
4	Analysis of potential funding sources									
5	Agreement on BioINSouth HUB's mission and vision						31/03/2025			
6	Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus						31/03/2025			
7	Regional stakeholder engagement						Ongoing	Extend invitations to HUB KoM		
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU						31/03/2025			
9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning						31/03/2025	Date of HUB KoM becomes known to WPs At least one meeting/ HUB (reporting templates will be provided by WPs)		
10	Online/ in-person/ hybrid Kick-off Meeting (KoM)						30/04/2025			
11	MoU signature and HUB establishment						30/04/2025	1 MoU / HUB member >= 15 members		

Figure 2: HUB establishment working plan Template

Information highlighted in yellow (linked to Time Frame and Success Criteria) should be respected, aligned with WP3 and DoA needs.

Due to timeline considerations, CTA recommended all the HUB's coordinators prepare as much information as possible in advance and confirm it with MARG members during the KOM, including a first working plan complete draft version, and some ideas regarding:

- 1) Stakeholders to be invited to join the HUB
- 2) Analysis of potential funding sources
- 3) BioINSouth HUB's mission and vision
- 4) BioINSouth primary areas of focus
- 5) Elements to be included in the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU
- 6) Potential HUB's Kick-off Meeting Dates.

5.3 Registration and venue

Registration were done by the regional/national HUBs coordinators using their usual platforms and procedures. All data were managed according to the FAIR principles and good data management practices as well as BioINSouth guidelines for personal data, which are GDPR compliant, avoid transferring personal data amongst partners. It was recommended to ask the attendees for the following information:

- Name
- Gender
- e-mail
- Company
- Position

5.4 Required equipment, support material, logistics

After the event, the presentations were sent to attendees by email, together with an event quality/satisfaction survey.

In case the event was done face-to-face, coffee or cocktail catering, name tags, project communication material (BioINSouth brochures) and participant packages should be provided by the regional/national HUBs coordinators.

As for the participant package, this could include a copy of all the presentations used during the event and corporate communication materials from the regional partners as desired.

The satisfaction survey was shared among participants at the end of the event as hard copy and gathered back filled in before the end of the event.

For justification purposes, a signature sheet was prepared and circulated among participants during the event.

In case the event was done online, each host could decide on the most suitable platform for such purpose.

It was strongly recommended to develop templates prefilled by the regional/national HUBs coordinators to have a basis on which to build on and discuss during the presentation of the questionnaire and interviews results, the HUBs concept and main guidelines.

5.5 Attendees

Main target audience for these events are MARG members, but other regional/national experts could be invited. A well-balanced combination of profiles from the quadruple helix was desirable.

Attendees' invitation

An example of the email that can be sent to invited MARG members is provided below so partners can adapt it to the local language, etc.

Dear Mr./Ms.:

As you may know, [name of host] is participating in the BioINSouth project (website link), funded by the European Commission. This project aims to **establish regional HUBs bringing together a broad range of stakeholders**, including policymakers and public authorities, expert voices, market actors (especially SMEs) and civil society (especially NGOs). The methodology will also seek the collaboration and exchange of best practices among the HUBs within a **macro-regional BioINSouth Network and with international organizations**. Additionally, the BioINSouth project looks for supporting decision-makers to incorporate considerations of ecological limits into their regional bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps, when it comes to circular bio-based activities by developing guidelines and digital tools, considering the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) assessment framework, to support the adoption of innovative methodologies to assess environmental impacts in multiple industrial bio-based systems, increasing regional competitiveness and innovation capacity, and contributing to the EU fair & green transition.

In the frame of the project, given your expertise in the field and your role as member of the Multi Actor Regional Group (MARG), we invite you to participate in the [Final name of the event], where you can hear in detail about the project and will participate in a co-creation exercise to set the working plan for design and implement the HUB at regional level, during the following year.

This event will take place **face-to-face/online on xxx from xxxh to xxh**.

The planned program is as follows: [it can be inserted here as text or the link to the online agenda can be provided]

Please feel free to register here [registration link] // or confirm by answering this email.

Thank you for your attention. We hope this initiative will be of interest to you.

Kind regards

5.6 Mail to be sent after the event

Once the event was finished, an email was sent to attendees, including all the materials used during the event and the satisfaction survey. An example of this email is provided below:

Dear attendee,

Thank you so much for join us during the [Final name of the event].

Enclosed/Here[[hyperlink](#)] you can find the materials used during the event. Also, please feel free to check the project website to be regularly updated about the BioINSouth project progress and results [WEBISTE LINK].

It would be nice if you could answer the following satisfaction survey and provide your feedback about the event. It would not take you more than five minutes!

This information is very important for us to improve upcoming activities and to offer you the most relevant event contents and formats.

Best regards,

.....

5.7 Satisfaction survey

Once the event was finished or about to end, hosts should gathered feedback from the attendees in order to assess the success of the action and to learn about attendees' expectations, potential overlooks that might have occurred or tentative improvements that can be considered in further events.

An example of the satisfaction survey can be found below.

Satisfaction survey

With the aim of gathering information about your experience at the [Name of the event], we have created this survey. Your input will help us in the planning and implementation of future activities.

This survey will take no longer than 5 minutes. Thank you very much for your collaboration.

**Mandatory*

Please, evaluate the following aspects of the event:

- *Organisation **
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- *Relevance of the topic and content **
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- *Level of the speakers (quality and clarity) **
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)
- *Participation and dialogue with the audience **
From 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent)

Please, write below any comment or feedback about the event and/or the work plan ahead at regional level within the BioINSouth project.

.....

Thank you!

If the event is done face-to-face, an additional question related to the location and catering can be included.

6 MARG KOMs organization and results

Main results and outcomes of the MARG KOMs organized for the BioINSouth regions/countries by the BioINSouth HUBs coordinators following the previous guidelines are provided next (in alphabetical order):

6.1 Andalusian MARG KOM

6.1.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

“Lanzamiento del Multi Actor Regional Group (MARG) en Andalucía” (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Andalusia KOM: Event creative used for social media.

Regional customization

CTA conducted the agenda entirely in Spanish to maximize participation and ensure that language was not a barrier, especially considering that most stakeholders were from Andalusia and might find English a limiting factor. Given that the event focused on the launch of the regional hubs in Andalusia, it was more effective and inclusive to use the local language.

CTA highlighted the presence of Mar Cátedra, Technical Advisor at the General Secretariat for Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development of the Regional Government of Andalusia (Junta de Andalucía).

Agenda

Lanzamiento del Multi Actor Regional Group (MARG) en Andalucía

Palacio de Ferias y Congresos de Málaga (FYCMA)

- | | |
|------------------------|--|
| 15:30h – 16:00h | Presentación del proyecto BioINSouth y el rol de los MARGs |
| 16:10h – 16:30h | Resultados de las entrevistas y feedback de otros MARGs |
| 16:30h – 17:30h | Plan de trabajo para la confirmación del BioINSouth Hub en Andalucía: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - De dónde partimos - A dónde queremos ir - Cómo conseguirlo |

 Co-funded by the European Union and supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members, under Grant Agreement No 101156363. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.

Figure 4: Andalusia KOM: Agenda of the event

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: March 13, 2025

Host: Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA)

Registration: The registration form² was hosted on the landing page created for the event on CTA's website.

Venue: Palacio de Ferias y congresos de Málaga (FYCMA)

The landing page is included in the [Annex V](#).

Figure 5: Andalusia KOM: Photos taken during the BioINSouth event at TRANSFIERE.

Required equipment, material, logistics

Each participant received a CTA-branded folder containing customized materials specifically prepared for the event. These included the event agenda and a quality assessment questionnaire. In addition, attendees were provided a BioINSouth brochure translated into Spanish by CTA (see [Annex V](#)). A signature list was also prepared using the official BioINSouth template.

As part of the intensive preparation activity performed by CTA for the KOM, and to ensure that all attendees had access to the necessary information, a shared folder was created prior to the event. The CTA team uploaded various documents relevant to the KOM and generated a QR code to facilitate real-time access for participants during the event.

² <https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/eventos/lanzamiento-multi-actor-regional-group-marg-andalucia/>

This folder included all the relevant documents linked to the activities for the Andalusian BioINSouth HUB implementation plan presented and validated during the KOM:

- 1) Presentations from the KOM regarding the BioINSouth project and the implementation workplan (excel file and PPT).
- 2) Preliminary regional stakeholders mapping (action 1).
- 3) Regional analysis report (action 2).
- 4) Presentation of the regional case study (action 3).
- 5) Repository with potential funding sources (action 4).
- 6) Draft for the Andalusian BioINSouth HUB Terms of Reference (ToR), Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) (actions 5 and 8).
- 7) HUB regional stakeholder engagement database (action 10).

Further details regarding the documents and shared folder can be found in *Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan*. [Figure 6](#) shows the access to the shared folder presented during the event (left) and the documents present in the shared folder (right).

Figure 6: BioINSouth Andalucía Shared Folder

Registrations:

A total of 17 people were registered to the event, including 3 from the private sector, 7 from academia and 2 from local governments, 2 from civil society and 3 from CTA (private sector). 81% of the MARG members invited had registered.

- Marina Barquero, female, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- María García Alegre, female, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- Cristina Cabeza, female, Andalucía TRADE, Head of the Agri-food Sector.
- José A. Camacho, male, University of Granada, head of research group.

- María del Mar Cátedra, female, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water, and Rural Development of the Government of Andalusia, Technical Advisor.
- Carla del Cerro, female, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- Francisco Javier Egea, male, University of Almería, Director of the Cajamar Chair of Circular Bioeconomy.
- Manuel Ibañez, male, Austral Venture Gestión SGEIC, Managing Partner.
- María Luisa Iglesia, female, Institute of Marine Research (INMAR) - University of Cádiz, Management and Communication Technician.
- José Antonio La Cal, male, BIOLIZA, CEO.
- María Dolores La Rubia, female, university of Jaén, professor.
- Pedro Luis Lázaro, male, Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (UCAUCE), president.
- Concepción Mira, female, TEPRO Consultores Agrícolas SL, Head of R&D Department.
- Juan Moreno, male, Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (UCAUCE), Secretary General.
- Francisco Javier Navas, male, Fundación ANDALTEC I+D+i, Head of the New Developments Department.
- Mercedes Rodríguez, female, Instituto de Desarrollo Regional. Universidad de Granada, director.
- Samir Sayadi, male, IFAPA. Department Agricultural Economics, Coordinator Researcher.

6.1.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

A total of 16 people attended the KOM, including 1 from the private sector, 8 from academia and 2 from local governments and 2 from civil society representatives and 3 from CTA (private sector). The 62% of the MARG members invited attended.

- Marina Barquero, female, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- Cristina Cabeza, female, Andalucía TRADE, Head of the Agri-food Sector.
- José A. Camacho, male, University of Granada, head of research group.
- Juan Castilla, male, University of Almería,
- María del Mar Cátedra, female, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water, and Rural Development of the Government of Andalusia, Technical Advisor.
- Rafael Dueñas, male, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- María García, female, Technological Corporation of Andalusia, consultant.
- María Luisa Iglesia, female, Institute of Marine Research (INMAR) - University of Cádiz, Management and Communication Technician.
- María Dolores La Rubia, female, University of Jaén, professor.
- Pedro Luis Lázaro, male, Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (UCAUCE), president.
- Juan Moreno, male, Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (UCAUCE), Secretary General.
- Concepción Mira, female, TEPRO, Consultores Agrícolas,
- Francisco Javier Navas, male, Fundación ANDALTEC I+D+i, Head of the New Developments Department.
- Marta Victoria Peláez, female, University of Almería
- Mercedes Rodríguez, female, Instituto de Desarrollo Regional. Universidad de Granada, director.

- Samir Sayadi, male, IFAPA. Department Agricultural Economics, Coordinator Researcher.

The signature list is included in the [Annex V](#).

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop

During the initial segment of the workshop, María García briefly presented the BioINSouth project. The complete presentation utilized during the event is included as an annex to this report (see [Annex V](#)).

The presentation was translated into Spanish to make the session more comprehensible and to ensure that the information was well understood by all MARG members during the meeting.

Figure 7: María García [CTA] presenting BioINSouth project. The BioINSouth Context.

The objectives of the workshop can be summarized as:

- Officially introduce the members of the Regional Multi-Actor Group (MARG) in Andalusia,
- Present the regional case study analysis, from the interviews results,
- Conduct a co-creation exercise to define the work plan for the BioINSouth HUB in Andalusia implementation.

These objectives were previously communicated to the MARG members by email and published for all audiences on the CTA website³.

Figure 8: María García [CTA] presenting (A) the members of the MARG Andalucía and (B) the workplan for the creation of the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía.

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis

The analysis of the Andalusian case study was presented to the MARG members through a PowerPoint presentation that is available as an annex to this report (see Annex V) and in the shared folder. The information provided was an overview derived from the four interviews with selected MARG members with experience in the Andalusian bioeconomy sector. These individuals were chosen for their extensive expertise and regional perspective. Based on their background and profiles, the two types of interviews were conducted. The four interviewees were:

Table 3: MARG Andalucía members interviewed.

First name	Last name	Stakeholder Category	Organisation	Position
Mar	Cátedra	Local governments	Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development (CAPADR)	Technical adviser
José Antonio	Camacho	Academic institutions	University of Granada	University professor
Francisco Javier	Navas	Academic institutions	Andaltec	Dr.-Eng. & MBA
Juan Moreno	Rodríguez	Civil society	Consumers' Union	General Secretary

³ [Lanzamiento del Multi Actor Regional Group \(MARG\) en Andalucía - Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía CTA](#)

The Andalusian case study sets out several key conclusions that were presented during the KOM. Among them, **the identification and availability of biomass raw materials** is a critical element for the development of biorefineries and regional bioeconomy. Potential constraints to biomass utilization were discussed, highlighting the need to address technical, economic, and regulatory barriers. **Technological innovation** is a vital element, with advancements in bioprocessing and collaborative efforts identified as essential for promoting regional biorefineries over traditional production systems. The interviews also underscored the importance of **developing robust economic metrics and models to ensure the sustainability of biorefineries**, as well as understanding their broader economic and social impacts, particularly in disadvantaged regions and developing countries.

Furthermore, it is emphasized that **favorable political frameworks and strategic collaborations** are essential to overcome existing barriers and drive the circular bioeconomy forward. Overall, the findings suggest that leveraging technological innovation, supportive policies, and effective stakeholder collaboration are key to enhancing the regional bioeconomy and ensuring the long-term viability of biorefineries in Southern Europe.

Although there were no specific comments to the case study results, these were used by some MARG members to contextualize future reflections for the development of the regional BioINSouth HUB Andalucía, such as referring to other potential sources of biomass that had been identified in the interviews and highlighted during the presentation.

Results/evidence from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan

During the second part of the event, the workplan for creating the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía was presented using a PowerPoint presentation (see [Annex V](#)), highlighting the context and differences between the MARG and the BioINSouth HUB, outlining the activities and objectives of each group.

All the MARG members were mentioned so that every invitee knew who was involved (11 out of the 14 members attended the event).

All relevant information was uploaded to a shared OneDrive folder, and the link was provided to all members so that everyone could review and agree on the details presented.

The final workplan, as shown in [Table 4](#), was agreed upon with the MARG members, and a deadline of March 31, 2025, was set to allow sufficient time for reviewing the documents and adding comments on nearly all actions.

Relevant agreements and comments gathered during the event were:

1. Action 5: BioINSouth HUB for Andalucía's mission and vision. Agreement of the BioINSouth HUB for Andalucía's mission and vision. During the meeting, the vision and mission were presented and agreed with MARG members.

- The **Mission** of the BioINSouth HUB in Andalucía is the development of a regional circular bioeconomy space to merge and coordinate inputs and activities from regional actors and stakeholders, following a territorial approach.
- The **Vision** of the BioINSouth HUB in Andalucía is to contribute to the implementation of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster planned in the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, advancing on some preparatory steps under the BioINSouth project framework.

2. Action 6: Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus. Pre-identification of the most relevant areas of action of the BioINSouth Hub in the Andalusia region. During the meeting, a survey was conducted with several questions prepared by the leader of WP4.

3. Action 8: Preparation of the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB Terms of Reference (ToR) and Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). Development of the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB (1) ToR including the framework for participation in the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB and (2) MoU to formalize the commitment of the Parties with the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB. Both documents were presented, and some of the members signed the MoU on site. The collaboration and agreement with the regional government was necessary to define the terms in which the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía could contribute to other regional initiatives.

The final discussion focused on identifying potential stakeholders for the HUB, with suggestions to prioritize cooperatives; federations of agro-food cooperatives; companies involved in biogenic and urban waste; technological centers; professional associations; entrepreneurial companies in the bioeconomy, including both success and failure cases; financial institutions; and other clusters.

Figure 9 shows the MARG members who participated in the discussion.

Figure 9: MARG members participating in the open discussion on the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía Work Plan.

Table 4: Workplan for the BioINSouth HUB Andalucía

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Andalusia						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping	To identify and analyse the key relevant stakeholders who play a significant role in the regional bioeconomy and could be potential actors for the Regional BioINSouth HUB . The quadruple helix approach will be always approached in the analysis.	<p>1) CTA will analyze the selection of the most suitable stakeholders for circular bioeconomy development based on its experience and participation in various initiatives.</p> <p>2) CTA will create a stakeholders database</p> <p>3) The database will be shared with MARG members for its review and completion if needed.</p> <p>(The database will be updated during the whole project duration as part of the HUB implementation)</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 database of relevant stakeholders	The database may become outdated or may not include relevant regional stakeholders	Regular review and update of the database of stakeholders to ensure it remains comprehensive and up to date

D2.1. Regional case studies

2	Regional needs assessment	<p>The objective of this action is based on the need to understand and update the regional needs, to develop appropriate actions at regional level accordingly, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identification of key sectors and industries with growth potential in the bioeconomy. -Updating of biomass resources in the region - Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the region's bioeconomy. - Identification of challenges and barriers to be addressed for bioeconomic development. 	<p>1) CTA will develop a document including all the information on the objectives.</p> <p>2) The report will be shared with MARG members for its review and completion, if needed.</p> <p>(The report will be updated during the whole project duration as part of the HUB implementation)</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 Report about Regional Needs	Not enough data/information available	Defined methodology to update the information/Contact key stakeholders
3	Analysis of pilot case studies	Identification of relevant information for the development of the regional bioeconomy and definition of growth scenarios for the BioINSouth HUB.	<p>1) 4 MARG members give semi-structured interviews to CTA, aiming at gathering information to define scenarios of growth of BioINSouth HUBs in Andalusia.</p> <p>2) A comprehensive analysis of the information retrieved during the interviews will be developed by CTA and shared with MARG members for its review and completion, if needed.</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 Presentation with the analysis of the MARGs' interviews.	Partial or biased information by respondent profile	Complementarity in the profile of respondents and feedback from the rest of MARG members on the results.

D2.1. Regional case studies

4	Analysis of potential funding sources	The objective of this action is the identification of possible sources of funds and an analysis of financing opportunities for the development of the regional bioeconomy.	<p>1) CTA will review and analyze potential programs of public funding and sources of private funding and potential investors at regional, national and European level for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects.</p> <p>2) CTA will create a diversified funding portfolio with the information obtained.</p> <p>3) The portfolio will be shared with MARG members for its review and completion if needed.</p> <p>(The portfolio will be updated during the whole project duration as part of the HUB implementation)</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 Portfolio with funding opportunities for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects in Andalusia.	Not enough data available The portfolio may become easily outdated.	Defined methodology to identify sources of funds/financing. Portfolio periodic updates.
5	BioINSouth HUB for Andalusia's mission and vision	Agreement of the BioINSouth HUB for Andalusia's mission and vision	<p>1) CTA will present a pre-definition for the BioINSouth HUB for Andalusia actionable steps (Mission) and long-term impacts (Vision).</p> <p>2) Both the mission and the vision will be discussed and finetuned with the MARGs members</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Agreed definition of the mission and vision of the BioINSouth HUB Andalusia.	Difficulty in reaching an agreement on the mission and vision	Discussion based on some initial draft information, to guide it.
6	Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus	Pre-identification of the most relevant areas of action of the BioINSouth Hub in the Andalusia region.	<p>1) Identification methodology (brief questionnaire) developed by BioINSouth.</p> <p>2) MARGs members are asked to give their opinion by filling it in (to be done within the MARG KOM).</p>	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	13/03/2025	Answers from MARGs	Low response rate	The questionnaire is easy to complete, and answers will be asked during the MARG KOM.

D2.1. Regional case studies

7	Regional stakeholder engagement	Engagement of relevant regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix to join the BioINSouth HUB in Andalusia (KPI 15-30).	1) Reidentification with MARG members of relevant stakeholders to be included in the HUB 2) Definition of an engagement strategy among CTA and MARGs during the MARG KOM	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Invitations to potential HUB members (15-30)	Low engagement	Develop D&C material explaining the benefits of joining the HUB at entity and regional level. Rely on MARG for supporting the engagement strategy desing and implementation.
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB Terms of Reference (ToR) and Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	Development of templates for the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB (1) ToR including the framework for participation in the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB and (2) MoU to formalize the commitment of the Parties with the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB	1) CTA develop final draft documents 2) MARG members are asked for their feedback and suggestions.	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 ToR agreed document 1 MoU agreed template	Lack of agreement between MARGs members	Discussion based on some initial draft information, to guide it.
9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning	Preparation activities for the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB KOM including date definition, event preparation actions, or B2B meetings with potential HUB members as part of an awareness-raising campaign and data collection.	1) Agreement of a suitable date and format (online/presence) with MARG members. 2) CTA will coordinate the event preparation. MARG members may be asked to support with some specific needs.	CTA	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Agreed date for the HUB KOM	Delays and difficulties in the preparation of the event	Support from CTA's communications team

D2.1. Regional case studies

10	BioINSouth Andalusia HUB KOM	This action has the objective of establishing the BioINSouth HUB Andalusia and is marked by the organisation of the KOM and the creation of a network of 15 to 30 stakeholders (by signing the MoU).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The establishment of the stakeholder network; 2) Communication plan of the activities related to the HUB; 3) The launch and definition of specific activities that are aligned with the strategic objectives of the bioeconomy. <p>These activities mark the establishment of the Andalusia HUB.</p>	CTA	Regional stakeholders	Human Resources	30/04/2025	<p>1 HUB KOM event</p> <p>Official launch for the BioINSouth Andalusia HUB (15-30 members)</p>	Not reaching the minimum of 15 members in the Andalusian HUB.	<p>Solid preparation of the event and of the information campaigns on the HUB and its benefits at institutional and regional level.</p> <p>Support in MARG members as prescriptors of the initiative.</p>
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Satisfaction survey results

Figure 10 shows participant assessments for four key parameters—Organization, Space and Material Resources, Relevance of Content and Subject Matter, and Participation and Dialogue Among Participants—each measured on a 1–5 scale (1 = lowest satisfaction, 5 = highest). The consistently high scores, all between 4 and 5, suggest minimal variance and indicate a uniformly positive perception of the event’s coordination, the adequacy of the materials provided, the pertinence of the topics covered, and the level of engagement fostered among attendees. This uniformity across multiple dimensions underscores the effectiveness of the BioINSouth MARG KOM. All surveys can be found in Annex V.

Figure 10: Quality Assessment Questionnaire for the BioINSouth MARG KOM

6.2 Asturias MARG KOM

6.2.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

“Reunión de lanzamiento del MARG de Asturias / Asturias MARG Kick off Meeting”

The invitation to MARG was not publicly spread. Emails were sent to the corresponding partners and other relevant actors for HUB building. However, ASINCAR posted the KoM on their social media⁴

Regional customization:

Language of the meeting was Spanish to ease and promote discussion. The venue, date and timeslot selected for the meeting was voted by all the participants offering different locations. Finally, the meeting was held on March 25, 2025, at ASINCAR facilities.

To prepare the agenda, as well as the gathering, some previous meetings were performed by the ASINCAR team. A meeting of INTERREG 3F GREEN MODELS (06/03/2025) was attended. This is another European initiative to promote bioeconomy in the region. Through this meeting, BioINSouth and the Catania forum were presented, and the synergies and needs of regional bioeconomy were discussed. The idea of these meetings is to take advantage and merge the work performed with different proposals that share the same aim.

Moreover, the ASINCAR team met David Villar (03/03/2025) as policymaker representative also to listen about the political perspective and view of Asturias bioeconomy. They defined interesting use cases to be included within the HUB and MARGs activities.

Finally, ASINCAR has also been in touch with Grupo DEX that leads a consortium of 18 entities of Asturias (AgroOE), which aims to promote sustainable agri-food practices. In line with the intention of sharing capacities, knowledge and experience with similar initiatives, ASINCAR is discussing with Grupo DEX about the different roles of both initiatives to define their boundaries and established synergies. Hence, ASINCAR has introduced BioINSouth project and HUB, to engage AgroOE consortium entities to join on 26th of March (Figure 11).

⁴ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/asincarr_carrusel-de-im%C3%A1genes-activity-7310273655110885377-

[sPTS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAwmgkgBCIM6Nh_CpOtjuzjkkRE8kjbuaOk](https://www.facebook.com/asincarrCT/posts/1081397494033600)

<https://www.facebook.com/asincarrCT/posts/1081397494033600>

https://www.instagram.com/p/DHnzORONE9d/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==

Figure 11: BioINSouth presentation to AGROOE consortium members by Cristina Viera (ASINCAR).

Considering the information and line of action identified through these meetings, ASINCAR curated ToR and MoU of HUB and further defined the implementation plan, potential use case and entities to be involved. All this information was considered to define the agenda.

Agenda:

A copy of the original agenda document (in Spanish) distributed within the invitation email is included below ([Figure 12](#)).

Multi-Actor Regional Group (MARG) Kick of Meeting Agenda

Localización: ASINCAR - Polígono La Barreda, C/ Solellero 5, CP 33180 Noreña

Horario: 12:00h – 14:00h

12:00h-12:15h – Recepción de invitados y café de bienvenida

12:15h-12:30h – Breve presentación del proyecto BioINSouth

- Objetivos
- Socios
- Línea de actuación

12:30h-13:00h – EL MARG asturiano

- Miembros del MARG de Asturias
- Contribuciones y rol
- Actividades realizadas por los miembros

13:00h- 13:55h – Construcción del BioINSouth HUB

- Encuesta sobre líneas de actuación del HUB
- Situación de la bioeconomía en Asturias
- Misión y visión
- Áreas de interés del HUB
- Posibles participantes y entidades involucradas en el HUB
- Potenciales fuentes de financiación
- Reunión de lanzamiento del HUB (posibles fechas)
- Revisión de documentos (ToR y MoU)

13:55h-14:00h – Conclusiones finales

14:00h – Tentempié de despedida

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Circular Bio-based Europe
JOINT UNDERTAKING

Figure 12: Asturias MARG KoM agenda

Date, host, registration and venue:**Date:** 25th of March 2025**Host:** ASINCAR**Registration:** Google Forms and email confirmation**Venue:** ASINCAR facilities

Images of the attendees, facilities and location were taken along the meeting are included in [Figure 13](#).

Figure 13: Photos obtained during Asturias MARG KOM were attendees, site distributions and resources used are observed.

Required equipment, material, logistics:

ASINCAR organized the meeting in one of its classrooms endowed with TV to share presentations. The tables and chairs were displaced in U form to facilitate interaction and discussion among attendees. They contracted a catering company that provided a welcome coffee break and farewell snack.

Moreover, each attendee received a printed copy of the MoU and ToR for HUB development, along with an ASINCAR folder and a pen. Copies of the slides, ToR and MoU that served as guidance for the discussion are attached to this report as [Annex VI](#).

Registrations

A total of 11 attendees registered at MARG KoM, with a final participation of 10. [Table 5](#) shows a detailed list of the participants indicating the name, gender, their position and their corresponding role in BioINSouth project. Regarding gender, 81,8% of registered participants were female. Distribution by stakeholder category are: private sector (54,5%), local governments (18,2%), academic institution (18,2%) and civil society (9,1%). It is important to remark that some of the attendees exhibited capacities that represent several of these categories such as the case of Cecilia Díaz Méndez that covers academia and civil society, and Noemí Trabanco Martín and María Menéndez Fernández that as consultants collaborate with private sector but also academia. Seven of eight of the Asturias MARG members registered (87,5%), with a final participation of six (75%)

Table 5: List of participants registered to Asturias MARG KoM event.

Name	Gender	Entity/Position	Role in BioINSouth	Stakeholder category
Beatriz García Fanjúl	Female	Innovasturias /Director	MARG member	Private sector
David Villar García	Male	Regional minister / Director General of Custody and Interior Territory	MARG member	Local governments
Cecilia Díaz Méndez	Female	University of Oviedo/ Full Professor at Sociology Department	MARG member	Academic institution /Civil society
Ana Elena Fernández Monzón	Female	SEKUENS Agency / Project technician	MARG member	Local governments
Sandra Sánchez García	Female	PTEBi cluster / General manager	MARG member	Private sector
Marta Fernández Pérez	Female	Educational Center Escultor Villanueva / Professor of Food Industries	MARG member	Civil society
Laura Faba Peón	Female	University of Oviedo/ Associated Professor of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Technology Department	MARG member	Academic institution
Juan Díaz García	Male	ASINCAR /General manager	MARG coordinator	Private sector
Cristina Viera Bardón	Female	ASINCAR/ Project manager	MARG coordinator	Private sector
Noemí Trabanco Martín	Female	Grupo DEX/ Consultant	HUB partner	Private sector /Academia
María Menéndez Fernández	Female	Grupo DEX/Consultant	HUB partner	Private sector/ Academia

Only one MARG member was not able to register due to agenda limitations: Salvador Ordoñez García. He was represented by Laura Faba Peón.

6.2.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

Ten participants attended Asturias MARG KoM. Six are official MARG members, which represents 60% of the total stakeholders involved within the MARG. From the participants registered 91% finally attended the meeting with the only absence of Beatriz García Fanjúl that cancelled their participation due to an urgent issue.

Table 6 shows information regarding gender, their position, role within BioINSouth and stakeholder category. 80% of the attendees were females and the percentage of each stakeholder category representation were: local governments (20%), academic institution (20%), private sector (50%) and civil society (10%).

Table 6: List of attendees to Asturias MARG KoM.

Name	Gender	Entity/Position	Role in BioINSouth
David Villar García	Male	Regional minister / Director General of Custody and Interior Territory	MARG member
Cecilia Díaz Méndez	Female	University of Oviedo/ Full Professor at Sociology Department	MARG member
Ana Elena Fernández Monzón	Female	SEKUENS Agency / Project technician	MARG member
Sandra Sánchez García	Female	PTEBi cluster / General manager	MARG member
Marta Fernández Pérez	Female	Educational Center Escultor Villanueva / Professor of Food Industries	MARG member
Laura Faba Peón	Female	University of Oviedo/ Associated Professor of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Technology Department	MARG member
Juan Díaz García	Male	ASINCAR /General manager	MARG coordinator
Cristina Viera Bardón	Female	ASINCAR/ Project manager	MARG coordinator
Noemí Trabanco Martín	Female	Grupo DEX / Consultant	HUB partner
María Menéndez Fernández	Female	Grupo DEX / Consultant	HUB partner

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop

The introduction and presentation of the session information is included in the slides provided in [Annex VI](#), and attached as an image to this section, used to conduct the discussion. Briefly, an initial overview of BioINSouth project was performed indicating the period of execution, call and partners involved. BioINSouth webpage was also attached to the slides to delve deeper into the information. A general description of BioINSouth aims with a summary of the activities to be performed within the project was also provided.

In general, the objectives of the workshop were:

1. Officially present BioINSouth project, aims and partners to Asturias MARG member
2. Internal presentation of Asturias MARG members, outlining their profiles and their expected knowledge contributions to the project.
3. Define MARG members' contribution through the project, emphasizing the current need of HUB constitution
4. Discussing the activities already performed in the project.
5. Discussing Asturias' bioeconomy development and needs, considering crucial stakeholders and actors that need to be included in the HUB
6. Agree on HUB reference documents
7. Informing about upcoming events such as Catania Forum and 2nd HUB forum in July, encouraging their participation.

BioINSouth data & partners

<https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>

- Call: HORIZON-JU-CBE-2023
- Starting: 01 June 2024 - 31 May 2027
- 15 partners of 9 countries

• **Coordinadores:** **SPRING**
Italian Circular Bioeconomy Cluster

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BioINSouth aim

<https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>

- **Objetivo:** promover la bioeconomía circular en las regiones del sur de Europa.

- 1 región líder (BioEAST HUB)
- 8 regiones piloto
- 1 región que replica

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BioINSouth: un camino hacia el éxito

- Creación de un comité de expertos (MARG) – WP2
- Constitución de un HUB de entidades – WP3
- Desarrollo de herramientas digitales para el monitoreo de la bioeconomía – WP4
- Validación de metodologías y herramientas – WP5
- Creación de guías para actores políticos – WP6

Figure 14: Introduction and presentation of the session information.

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

The main topics to discuss and the final conclusions are provided here:

Results of semi-structured interviews. Three conclusions derived from the analysis of the answers received of the semi-structured interviews: 1- Asturias bioeconomy is still at its preliminary stages, and a lot of work needs to be done. 2- Biomass available in our regions is mainly agrifood, forestry and urban.

Results of the discussion: there was a full agreement on the Asturias bioeconomy stage. However, some of the attendees emphasize the need to consider other biomass such as that derived from livestock activity related to paper production, since in Asturias there is a very relevant industry (ENCE) that has recently switched its productive models. MARG members and attendees agreed on the positive impact on bioeconomy development to the region. However, this development needs to consider ecological boundaries and further align and transmit its advances to society and new generations.

BioINSouth: el MARG asturiano

- ¿Qué hacemos?
 - Contribuir al mapeo de la situación actual de la bioeconomía
 - Disponibilidad de biomasa, actores de interés
 - Nichos por explotar
 - Ayudar en la construcción del HUB (15-30 entidades)
 - Proporcionar vuestro conocimiento, visión, consejo e imagen
 - Cuestionario online
 - Entrevistas
 - Presentación de meet the MARGs members

Bioeconomía en Asturias: todavía queda bastante por hacer.
Biorrefinerías de biogás

Biomasa asturiana: agroalimentaria, urbana, forestal agroganadera, papelera/energía (ENCE)

Impacto de la bioeconomía: se ve positivo el impacto en materia laboral y reto demográfico pero debe de implantarse con cautela. Se necesita apoyo político, entender el movimiento de la economía, cuidar el impacto medioambiental. Preconcepto de biorrefinería

Figure 15: Slide to promote the discussion (including the results of the discussion)

HUB mission and vision

ASINCAR presented the mission and vision of the HUB as it is written in the ToR.

In general, it was accepted and agreed among the attendees. This point did not promote discussion.

BioINSouth: el HUB asturiano

- ToR incluido en el mail
- Misión: acciones para conseguir la visión
- Visión: la prospectiva

The Mission of the BioINSouth HUB in Asturias is to create a holistic network of crucial stakeholders that promotes the bioeconomy in Asturias region. To do so, Asturian BioINSouth HUB will reinforce and spread already applied bioeconomy strategies within the region to ensure their long-term maintenance. In addition, BioINSouth HUB Asturias will cooperate to identify underuse biomass, exploring the best approaches to exploit it.

The Vision is to contribute to the already identified objectives in Asturias circular strategy to sustain the sustainable transition of the region towards bioeconomy. By other means, the HUB will work to increase the number of circular fluxes identified between biomass provider and revalorization enterprises by the end of the project.

Figure 16: Asturias’s HUB mission and vision

HUB use cases definition

ASINCAR presented three use cases to be implemented within the Asturias HUB of BioINSouth: (1) biochar production from agri-food waste, (2) a comprehensive system for the cultivation and utilization of native fruit trees (apple, hazel, and chestnut), and (3) livestock residues and blue economy. For each use case, ASINCAR provided a list of potential biomass sources to be used as feedstock, proposed applications, and a set of potential stakeholders. This point sparked the most extensive discussion. Key issues raised included the need to address biomass availability, concerns that some of the proposed use cases were not economically or technologically viable, and that certain examples (e.g., biochar production) did not align with circular bioeconomy principles. As a result, it was concluded that the first step should be to identify the most feasible biomass sources to be exploited and then define the corresponding use cases and potential stakeholders.

BioINSouth: el HUB asturiano

Figure 17: Asturias's HUB use cases

Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan

ASINCAR, as MARG coordinator, presented an implementation plan to establish HUB in three phases (as state in ToR).

Phase 1 (April 2025-February 2026)

Aim: mapping of the bioeconomy strategy within Asturias considering relevant stakeholders and biomass availability within the region

Activities:

- Meetings within HUB entities to discuss the current needs and possibilities of bioeconomy within the region considering ecological boundaries
- Building a portfolio of the technological capabilities to exploit Asturias' biomass, identifying the underexplored niches
- Co-creation activities to define pilot/use cases and engage crucial stakeholders
 - First forum Catania 5th and 6th of June
 - Second forum Asturias July (TBC)
- Identifying funding opportunities at regional, national and European level
- Implementation of BioINSouth toolkit, interviews, surveys and questionnaires

Phase 2 (February 2026- February 2027)

Aim: promotion of BioINSouth HUB Asturias mission and vision within the region and integration of HUB activities with European perspective

Activities:

- Participation in funding calls at regional, national and European level considering the opportunities and needs agreed through phase 1

- Strengthening the European network established within the project to exchange knowledge, capacities and experience
 - Third forum Asturias
- Creation of thematic working groups (TWG) with defined roles
- Implementation of BioINSouth toolkit, interviews, surveys and questionnaires
- Development of political guidelines

Phase 3 (February 2027 – after BioINSouth project finish)

Aim: ensure BioINSouth HUB Asturias maintenance after project finish

Activities:

- Internal revision of the success and results of the previous phases
- Definition of a self-management plan
- Explore the conversion of BioINSouth HUB Asturias into a legal entity
- Interchange of good practices with other BioINSouth HUB

These activities will be supported by the Multi-Actor Regional Group (MARGs) that serves as the project's advisory body, offering knowledge and strategic direction. The Asturias MARGs is formed by 8 crucial actors of bioeconomy and innovation within the region.

These phases were generally agreed. Finally, MARG members accepted to: (1) contribute to mapping the current state of the bioeconomy, (2) assist in building the HUB (15-30 entities) and (3) provide their knowledge, vision, advice, and image through the HUB and project development.

BioINSouth: plan de implementación

Figure 18: Asturias’s HUB implementation plan

Finally, some relevant data and upcoming events were discussed:

- 22 April 2025 – Potential date for HUB KoM
- 01 July 2025 – Second Asturias BioINSouth HUB with the aim of performing co-creation activities to map and define the starting point for HUB and use case development.

Satisfaction survey results

The survey was provided as an online questionnaire in an email sent with a summary of the MARG KoM discussion and future steps. Link to the questionnaire is included⁵.

Only 4 answers were received that show a very positive evaluation of the KoM with all the questions receiving a score up to 4 of 5. The response document is attached in [Annex VI](#). As an aspect for improvement, one participant suggested to pre-define attendees' disposition in the room and to change it in the different events.

⁵ https://docs.google.com/forms/d/111Fj7bMfRhMUubP_v_6iZOUmydYdYLUXYpL2I IzzMBs/edit

6.3 Campania MARG KOM

6.3.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

BioINSouth Kick-off Meeting MARG Campania

Regional customization:

To enhance interaction among MARG members, the meeting was held in the local language. The agenda was largely based on the version proposed by WP2, with only slight modifications to the order of topics and the addition of information about the BioINSouth forum in Catania. The MARG Kick-off Meeting was intended exclusively for members, and no external stakeholders were invited.

Agenda:

10:00	Introduction: welcome to participants, brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the KoM
10:30	MARG: objectives, members, and roles within the project
10:45	Presentation of preliminary results from the analysis of regional/national case studies based on questionnaire responses and discussion
11:10	HUB and main guidelines
11:40	Questionnaire for areas of focus (QR code)
11:50	Coffee break
12:00	MARG work plan for the design and implementation of the HUB
12:45	BioINSouth Forum Catania, June 5-6, 2025
13:00	Satisfaction survey and conclusions

Original agenda included in [Annex VII](#).

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: March 18th, 2025

Host: University of Naples Federico II

Registration: via e-mail

Venue: face-to-face in Naples (Room Bakunin, Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Complesso di Monte Sant'Angelo, via Cintia 80126 Napoli).

Figure 19: Presentation to MARG members on the BioINSouth project and the main objectives of the Kick-Off Meeting

Figure 20: Discussion with Valeria Fascione (Regional Assessor - Research, Innovation and Start up, Italian Region Campania) regarding the HUB and its implementation.

Figure 21: Campania MARG members during the kick-off meeting

Required equipment, material, logistics:

For the Kick-off Meeting of MARG Campania, an email was sent to all MARG members inviting them to Naples and including the event agenda ([Annex VII](#)).

A week before the meeting, key documents for discussions such as the MARG work plan, the HUB adhesion form, and the HUB regulation were shared.

During the KoM, an attendance list was used to collect the signatures of all participants, while a laptop was used to display the PowerPoint presentation prepared for the occasion ([Annex VII](#)).

Regarding logistics, the host provided support with the room, networking coffee and technical system to ensure the successful execution of the event.

Registrations:

Table 7: List of registrations to Campania MARG KoM.

Name and surname	Gender	Entity	Position
Beatrice Cobucci Ponzano	Female	Institute of Biosciences and BioResources	MARG member
Concetta D'Orio	Female	BioTekNet	MARG member
Danilo Ercolini	Male	Centro Nazionale Agritech	MARG member
Danilo Porro	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team
Fabio Apone	Male	Novamont	MARG member
Francesco Caracciolo	Male	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Giancarlo Chiavazzo	Male	Legambiente	MARG member
Luigi Iavarone	Male	Iavarone Wood Technology	MARG member
Mario Bonaccorso	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team
Martino Di Serio	Male	University of Naples Federico II	MARG member
Nadia Mazzarella	Female	BioTekNet	MARG member
Pier Francesco Recchi	Male	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Pierluigi Argoneto	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team

A total of 13 people were registered to the event, including 4 from the private sector, 5 from research and academia, 1 from civil society and others for SPRING Team.

6.3.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

Table 8: List of attendees to Campania MARG KoM.

Name and surname	Gender	Entity	Position
Beatrice Cobucci Ponzano	Female	Institute of Biosciences and BioResources	MARG member
Concetta D'Orio	Female	BioTekNet	MARG member
Danilo Ercolini	Male	Centro Nazionale Agritech	MARG member
Danilo Porro	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team
Elena Cervelli	Female	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Fabio Apone	Male	Novamont	MARG member
Francesco Caracciolo	Male	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Giancarlo Chiavazzo	Male	Legambiente	MARG member
Giovanni Sannia	Male	Biopox	MARG member
Luigi Iavarone	Male	Iavarone Wood Technology	MARG member
Mario Bonaccorso	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team
Martino Di Serio	Male	University of Naples Federico II	MARG member
Nadia Mazzeola	Female	BioTekNet	MARG member
Nunzia Arillo	Female	Campania Region	MARG member
Pier Francesco Recchi	Male	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Pierluigi Argoneto	Male	SPRING	SPRING Team
Stefania Pindozi	Female	University of Naples Federico II	University of Naples Federico II Team
Valeria Fascione	Female	Campania Region	Councillor of Research, Innovation and Startup, Campania Region

A total of 18 people participated to the event, including 5 from the private sector, 7 from research and academia, 1 from civil society, 2 from policy makers and others for the SPRING Team.

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop:

The meeting opened with a comprehensive introduction to the BioINSouth project, setting the stage by emphasizing the pivotal role of stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes for the advancement of the bioeconomy. A key point of discussion was the existing gap between Northern and Southern Europe in this sector, underscoring the need for targeted efforts to bridge this divide. The distinction between MARG and HUB was carefully outlined: MARG, initially formed as informal, multi-stakeholder groups, is envisioned as a starting point for the creation of a more structured, officially

recognized regional HUB. These HUBs aim to function as permanent advisory bodies, continuing their activities beyond the project's lifespan to influence/support regional bioeconomy strategies. A notable highlight was the interest shown by the Campania region, which stands as a positive example of regional commitment to bioeconomy development. Campania's involvement in several bioeconomy-related projects signals its awareness of the sector as a key driving factor for regional growth and its openness to further investments. Furthermore, the long-term ambition of BioINSouth to extend this model beyond Europe – particularly to North Africa and the Middle East – was introduced, reflecting the project's broader vision of fostering international cooperation in bioeconomy development.

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

The analysis of the regional case study aimed to develop and test a methodology for an ex-ante evaluation of bioeconomy impacts, particularly focusing on the LULUCF sector, food security and biodiversity. This methodology integrates stakeholder participation, leveraging both questionnaires and interactive workshops, with this meeting serving as a clear example.

The presentation showcased key insights derived from the questionnaire responses. A generally positive perception emerged about bioeconomy's potential impact on land use and environmental outcomes. Nonetheless, the analysis also revealed existing barriers to development, predominantly related to lack of awareness regarding the opportunities provided by the sector and economic constraints, such as increased production costs.

Participants engaged actively with these findings, expressing general agreement with the outcomes and proposed scenarios. The subsequent discussion generated valuable reflections, particularly on the robustness and limitations of the employed methodology. Noteworthy points included considerations of urban surface expansion and how bioeconomy initiatives might interplay with such transformations, emphasizing the need for adaptable, region-specific approaches.

Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan:

This session focused on the practical steps and timelines for establishing the regional HUB, detailing its proposed structure, functions, and key milestones. A regulatory draft – shared with attendees ahead of the meeting for pre-review – was revisited to ensure clarity and alignment.

Participants were presented with a roadmap, outlining activities, responsibilities, and key deadlines to guide the HUB's creation. Notably, no major objections arose regarding the activity plan or the regulatory draft. However, the discussion provided an opportunity to clarify essential elements, particularly around the HUB's legal framework, terminology, and the expected level of commitment from members.

The consensus reached marks a promising step forward, with the group demonstrating both engagement and readiness to contribute to the HUB's establishment.

Campania workplan:

Premise

All eight HUBs of the BioINSouth project are tasked with developing an activity program by August 2025, which reflects the needs of local stakeholders and is, of course, aligned with regional objectives regarding the development of Bioeconomy.

One of the main objectives of the BioINSouth project is to highlight and outline development trajectories for local institutions, particularly concerning ecological limits (primarily land use and biodiversity loss) that must be considered when advancing various initiatives.

HUB Campania Activity Program (June 2025 – May 2026)

- Define the current state of development and identify the main areas of intervention in the various sectors of the Bioeconomy in Campania.
- Identify the institutions responsible for the development of the Bioeconomy in Campania.
- Identify the main public and private stakeholders.
- Identify 1-2 case studies.
- Test and develop the Toolkit created by Innen, available from July 2025.
- Define the Mission and Vision of the HUB Campania.
- Establish the first-year activities, including milestones.

Milestones

November 2025

1. Kick-off meeting, adoption of the HUB regulations and the membership form (pre-approved by MARG).
2. Initial mapping of regional stakeholders.
3. Launch of awareness campaigns.
4. Define the Mission and Vision.
5. Signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) by at least five new stakeholders, in addition to the founding HUB stakeholders.

February 2026

6. Identify and launch pilot case studies.
7. Ensure the alignment of the HUB's mission with:
 - Regional S3 Plan
 - Italian Bioeconomy Strategy
 - Ministry of Economic Development
 - Ministry of Agriculture, Food, and Forestry Policies
 - Ministry of University and Research

- Ministry of Environment and Protection of Land and Sea
 - Conference of Italian Regions and the Agency for Territorial Cohesion
 - National Technological Clusters (CLAN, BIG) and National Forestry Institutes
 - Relevant PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) projects, both national and regional.
8. Identify key local opportunities for the Campania region.
9. Identify key international opportunities for the Campania region.
10. Develop a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), including:
- Ambitions and expected impacts
 - Current and cross-cutting themes
 - Implementation strategy for the program
 - Annual work program and progress monitoring
 - Executive summary
 - Indicators and risks
 - Annual activity report and subsequent annual work plan
 - Ideas for overcoming barriers, etc.

May 2026

11. Identify the HUB's self-sustainability plan, including a business plan.
12. Identify key risks and a contingency plan.

Table 9: Working plan for the BioINSouth Campania HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members.

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Campania						
N°	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping	Identification of the QH stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy in Campania to be involved in the BioINSouth HUB Campania.	1) SPRING will create a database with the list of potential stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy development based on its experience and participation in various initiatives. 2) Feedbacks and considerations from MARG's members and the Assessor for Research, Innovation and Start up of Campania will be requested.	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	Database (excel file)	The database may not include all relevant stakeholders	Continue to map regional stakeholder and update the database
2	Regional needs assessment	Identification of regional needs and related opportunities in order to develop specific actions. Identification	1) SPRING will start to analyse the regional needs 2) The need will be introduced and jointly discussed with MARG's members 3) The needs must be continuously updated	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	List of needs/opportunities	This action does not involve big risks	N/A

D2.1. Regional case studies

		of the scientific and technological networks in the filed is also an objective.								
3	Analysis of pilot case studies	Definition of regional scenarios based on the information collected with the semi-structured interviews. Based on the answers, two scenarios will be projected.	1) SPRING performed more semi-structured interviews to MARG's members 2) The information will be analysed in a comprehensive way 3) Results will be shared to the MARG during the KOM, discussed and jointly validated	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	Presentation with the information collected from the semi-structured interviews	potential disagreement on the answers from other members	Ask for feedback during the KOM
4	Analysis of potential funding sources	Identification of the most relevant research and innovation opportunities	Analysys regional (Smart Specialization Strategy_S3), national and international opportunities	SPRING	MARG/HUB Campania	Human Resources	Continuous	List of potential funding sources	Underestimation of small, local funding sources	Continuous mapping
5	Agreement on BioINSouth HUB's Mission and Vision	Define Mission and Vision of HUB Campania	1) SPRING will present during the MARG KOM the Vision and the Mission of the HUB 2) MARG's members will be invited to provide comments/suggestions 3) Defnition of Mission	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	Final definition of the Mission and Vision of the HUB	This action does not involve big risks	N/A

D2.1. Regional case studies

			and Vision will be validated							
6	Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus	Identification and selection of the most relevant areas of action of the BioINSouth Hub in Capania.	1) MARGs members are asked to answer the questionnaire (QR code) during the KOM	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	18/3/2025	Answers from MARG members	This action does not involve big risks	N/A
7	Regional stakeholder engagement	Engage relevant regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix in the BioINSouth HUB in Campania.	1) Starting from the stakeholders present in the database, think about two rounds of invitations 2) Define the necessary documents for the engagement phase (e.g. membership form validated during the KOM)	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	30/4/2025	minimum 15 to 30 stakeholders involved	Involve a minimum of 15 stakeholder by the deadline	Start involving immediately after the MARG KOM and send reminders
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU	Develop templates for the engagement of local stakeholders in BioINSouth HUB in Campania: regulatory	1) development of the draft documents 2) validation from MARG members	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	Final regulatory and membership form	This action does not involve big risks	N/A

D2.1. Regional case studies

		draft and membership form.								
9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning	Organize the KOM of HUB Campania (date, logistics, invitations and agenda of the day)	1) Identify the date based on the availability of the room, SPRING team and MARG members 2) Organize the co-creation workshop including "state of the play"	SPRING	MARG Campania	Human Resources	31/3/2025	Agreed date	This action does not involve big risks	N/A
10	MoU signature and HUB establishment	Establish the BioINSouth HUB Campania	1) Engage QH stakeholders; 2) Formal establishment during the HUB KOM, based on the formal signatures received. 3) Start planning the activities of the HUB.	SPRING	MARG/HUB Campania	Human Resources	30/4/2025	1 MoU / HUB member >= 15 members	Involve minimum 15 stakeholder by the deadline	Be comprehensive in the engagement phase by explaining the benefits of joining the HUB

Satisfaction survey results:

All participants expressed a positive opinion about the meeting, highlighting the excellent organization, the quality of the content, and the high level of the speakers. The outcomes, constructive dialogue, and interactivity were also appreciated, fostering an open and productive exchange.

The discussion was well attended and the work finished after the scheduled time. We also analyzed and discussed all the satisfaction questions together with the participants and everyone, on all the questions, expressed a level of satisfaction in between good and excellent without leaving detailed comments.

6.4 Centro Region/Portugal MARG KOM

6.4.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

“Reunião de Arranque MARG do projeto BioINSouth”

Regional customisation:

The Kick-off meeting was conducted in the local language (Portuguese), and the key points provided in the guidelines were addressed. To better address regional needs, an extensive debate took place regarding the results from the interviews, with a focus on the regional reality. The regional authority responsible for defining bioeconomy funding calls was present (CCDR-Cento – Comissão de Coordenação da Região Centro), and their presence was considered relevant. The group size for this kick-off meeting was deliberately kept small to facilitate a fruitful discussion and prevent too many participants from broadening the discussion unnecessarily or losing focus.

Agenda:

10h Welcome Coffee

Introduction Session: Presentation of BioINSouth project and main objectives of both the project and the meeting.

Explanation of MARG concept and structure: Objectives, members and roles throughout BioINSouth project

Presentation of the concept of HUBs and main guidelines

Presentation of the preliminary results from regional study cases (interviews): Analysis based on the results of the interviews with subsequent discussion regarding the outputs. A brief analysis on the output of the Land use survey was also performed.

Co-creation of the workplan: Focused on the design and implementation of the HUB at regional level, during BioINSouth project

Other Comments/suggestions

Next steps

13h Networking Lunch

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: March 11, 2025

Host: Biocant Park, Cantanhede

Registration: Google forms⁶

Venue: Biocant Park, Cantanhede

The registration page is included in the [Annex VIII](#).

Figure 22: Photo taken during the BioINSouth event at Biocant Park.

Figure 23: Photo taken at the end of the BioINSouth event at Biocant Park prior to the networking lunch.

⁶https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeQCg6PTEu_50ZKS0bdxE_tYJ1jqkn2Ho4VhpN1uejzwsO7sg/viewform?usp=sharing

Required equipment, material, logistics:

PowerPoint presentation.

The signature list is included in [Annex VIII](#).

Registrations:

A total of 13 people were registered to the event, including 8 people from the academia, 2 from the private sector, 2 people from regional and local governments and one person from civil society.

Table 10: List of participants registered to Centro Region MARG KoM event.

Name	Gender	Entity	Position
Carlos Magalhães e Silva	Male	P-BIO	Project Manager
Elisabete Silvestre	Female	Cooperativa Agrícola de Coimbra	Board Member
Helena Vieira	Female	Universidade de Aveiro	Coordinator Researcher
Joana Branco	Female	Biocant Park	Innovation & Ecosystem Development Director
Lucas Coelho	Male	Stex/	Biorefinery Solutions Responsible
Luís Miguel Martins	Male	Food4Sustainability	Service Director
Mariana Paupério	Female	BlueBio Alliance	Senior Project Manager
Mário Fidalgo	Male	AD ELO	Executive Director
Miguel Moreira	Male	Universidade de Coimbra	Auxiliary Researcher
Nuno Gomes	Male	Câmara Municipal de Cantanhede	Assistant to the President's Support Office
Paula Castro	Female	Universidade de Coimbra & CR Inove	CR Inove Pivot for the Coimbra sub-region & Researcher at UC
Raquel Guedes	Female	P-BIO	Operations Manager
Sophie Patrício	Male	CCDR-Centro	Head of the Promotion, Innovation and Regional Competitiveness Division

6.4.2 MARG KOM Results**Participants:**

A total of 12 people joined the event, 7 representatives of academia (research institutes, technology parks and faculties), 2 representatives of private sector or company representatives, 1 representative of civil society and 2 representatives of regional and local authorities. 92% of the MARG members invited attended (12 out of 13 members).

Table 11: List of attendees to Centro Region MARG KoM.

Name	Gender	Entity	Position
Carlos Magalhães e Silva	Male	P-BIO	Project Manager
Elisabete Silvestre	Female	Cooperativa Agrícola de Coimbra	Board Member
Helena Vieira	Female	Universidade de Aveiro	Coordinator Researcher
Joana Branco	Female	Biocant Park	Innovation & Ecosystem Development Director
Lucas Coelho	Male	Stex/	Biorefinery Solutions Responsible
Mariana Paupério	Female	BlueBio Alliance	Senior Project Manager
Mário Fidalgo	Male	AD ELO	Executive Director
Miguel Moreira	Male	Universidade de Coimbra	Auxiliary Researcher
Nuno Gomes	Male	Câmara Municipal de Cantanhede	Assistant to the President's Support Office
Paula Castro	Female	Universidade de Coimbra & CR Inove	CR Inove Pivot for the Coimbra sub-region & Researcher at UC
Raquel Guedes	Female	P-BIO	Operations Manager
Sophie Patrício	Male	CCDR-Centro	Head of the Promotion, Innovation and Regional Competitiveness Division

The signature list is included in the [Annex VIII](#).

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop:

The objectives of the kick-off meeting can be summarized as:

- Officially introduce the members of the Regional Multi-Actor Group (MARG) in Centro Region-Portugal;
- Present the regional case study analysis, from the interviews results, followed by discussion;
- Collect opinion of every MARG member in the room regarding the work plan for the BioINSouth HUB in Centro Region-Portugal implementation;

These objectives were previously communicated to the MARG members by email and presented in the agenda.

The workshop began with a brief introduction to P-BIO, its mission and the reason for having applied to the call in which BioINSouth project was accepted. This brief introduction was performed via remote call by Filipa Sacadura, secretary general of P-BIO, followed by a short introduction to the BioINSouth project, delivered by Carlos Magalhães e Silva, project manager at P-BIO, evidence attached below).

Participants were given a detailed overview of the project, its objectives and how the multi-actor approach will contribute to the regional bioeconomy. The importance of the CCDR-Centro's presence was emphasized, given its influence in defining regional public funding policies for the bioeconomy.

To make the content more accessible and ensure clear communication, the presentation was done in Portuguese, but the PPT content was in English for a more accurate transmission of the information as well.

Discussion of Regional Case Studies:

The regional case studies were widely debated (starting with the interviews on biorefineries), with a focus on the opportunities and challenges for implementing the HUB. Among the main topics listed were:

- The need for an exhaustive survey of available natural and industrial resources;
- The impact of national and European regulations on the viability of projects in the bioeconomy sector;
- The difficulties faced by companies in adopting innovative solutions due to bureaucratic and financing barriers;
- The importance of sensitizing farmers and other local actors to the benefits of the bioeconomy;
- The identification of priority sectors for the HUB, such as the valorization of marine biomass, agro-industrial and urban waste and bioenergy.

Figure 24: Carlos Magalhães e Silva [P-BIO] presenting BioINSouth project and the BioINSouth Context.

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

The discussion was conducted in a roundtable format, as shown in the images above, and was recorded following the necessary authorization given verbally by all the presents in the meeting and discussion. The regional case studies were discussed at length (starting with the interviews on biorefineries), focusing on the opportunities and challenges for implementing the HUB. Among the main topics listed were:

- The need for an exhaustive survey of available natural and industrial resources.
- The impact of national and European regulations on the viability of projects in the bioeconomy sector.

- The difficulties faced by companies in adopting innovative solutions due to bureaucratic and financing barriers.
- The importance of sensitizing farmers and other local actors to the benefits of the bioeconomy.
- The identification of priority sectors for the HUB, such as the valorization of marine biomass, agro-industrial waste, urban waste and bioenergy.

The overall presentation is included in the [Annex VIII](#).

The basis information provided was an overview derived from the four interviews with selected MARG members with experience in the bioeconomy sector of the Centro Region. These individuals were chosen for their extensive expertise, regional perspective and complementarity. The four interviewees were:

Table 12: MARG Centro Region members interviewed.

First name	Last name	Stakeholder Category	Organisation	Position
Lucas	Coelho	Private Sector	Stex	Founder
Mário	Fidalgo	Civil Society	AD ELO	Executive Director
Joana	Branco	Private Sector	Biocant Park	Innovation & Ecosystem Development Director
Paula	Castro	Academic Institution	University of Coimbra	Invited Auxiliar Researcher

Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan:

For co-creation the discussion and definition of the regional HUB was one of the central points of the meeting, with the active participation of all the stakeholders. The main elements discussed were:

- Strategic objectives: defining clear goals for the HUB's impact on the regional economy.
- Necessary infrastructure: identifying essential physical spaces and equipment, as well as logistical issues.
- Financing models: exploring public and private funds to make the HUB viable.
- Inter-institutional collaboration: establishing partnerships with universities, research centers and companies.
- Capacity building and training: development of training programs to qualify the local workforce.
- Impact monitoring: creating indicators to assess the progress and success of the HUB over time.

Participants emphasized the importance of ensuring a participatory governance model in which the different players have an active voice in decision-making. Some additional suggestions included:

- Creating/fixing the advisory board with representatives from industry, academia and public administration.
- Promoting events and workshops to disseminate good practices and attract new partners.
- Implementing pilot projects to test innovative solutions before scaling them up.

- Adoption of digital technologies to facilitate collaboration and monitoring of the HUB's progress.

Next steps (until 31 March)

To consolidate the meeting's progress, the following next steps were defined:

- Drafting of this summary report and subsequent detailed strategy document, incorporating the participants' contributions
- Organizing a new meeting to present the HUB's final plan, namely mission and vision and focus areas
- Identifying sources of funding and submitting applications for European funds
- Mobilizing new partners interested in joining the HUB
- Develop a detailed timetable for implementing the proposed activities.
- Preparation of the Memorandum of Understanding for the Regional Hub
- Planning the Hub Kick-off Meeting (to be held by 30 April)
- Signing of the Memorandum of Understanding and 'formal' establishment of the Hub (to be held by 30 April) ≥ 15 members

The Mission and Vision were discussed and will be presented as all feedback considered in the kick-off meeting of the Hub.

Table 13: Workplan for the BioINSouth HUB Centro Region - PT

MAIN OBJECTIVE			Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Centro Region - PT							
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping	To identify, analyse and invite the key relevant stakeholders who play a significant role in the regional bioeconomy and could be potential actors for the Regional BioINSouth HUB following the quadruple helix approach.	1) P-BIO will analyze the selection of the most suitable stakeholders for circular bioeconomy development based on its experience and participation in various initiatives. 2) MARG Members will also suggest suitable stakeholders to be involved and to be added to the stakeholders' database 3) The database will be shared (on a shared folder) with MARG members for its review and completion if needed.	P-BIO	MARG Members	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 database of relevant stakeholders	The database may not be representative by not including all or a significant part of the relevant regional stakeholders	Frequently review and update of the database of stakeholders to ensure that the database is regularly updated and representative

D2.1. Regional case studies

2	Regional needs assessment	<p>The objective of this action is based on the need to understand and update the regional needs, to develop appropriate actions at regional level accordingly, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identification of priority areas and value chains with growth potential in the bioeconomy. -Evaluate biomass resources in the region - Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the region's bioeconomy. - Identification of challenges and barriers to be addressed for bioeconomic development. 	<p>1) P-BIO will draft a preliminary document (report) that is also the basis for the definition of mission and vision and priority areas of focus.</p> <p>2) The report will be shared (shared folder) with MARG members for its review.</p> <p>(The documents can be updated during the project duration as part of the HUB implementation)</p>	P-BIO	MARG Members / HUB member representatives	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 Report about Regional Needs	Not representative / Informative enough	Involvement of the MARG Members and later on the HUB member representatives / key stakeholders
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D2.1. Regional case studies

3	Analysis of pilot case studies	Identification of relevant information for the development of the regional bioeconomy and definition of growth scenarios for the BioINSouth HUB.	<p>1) 4 MARG members give semi-structured interviews to P-BIO, aiming at gathering information to define scenarios of growth of BioINSouth HUBs in Centro Region.</p> <p>2) A comprehensive analysis of the information retrieved during the interviews will be developed by P-BIO and shared with MARG members for discussion in MARG kick-off meeting. Further review will be made with inputs by MARG members.</p>	P-BIO	MARG Members	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 Presentation with the analysis of the MARGs' interviews.	Biased information because of limited number of interviews	Feedback from the MARG members on the results and further completion.
4	Analysis of potential funding sources	Identification of possible funding sources for the development of the regional bioeconomy and HUB continuity.	<p>1) P-BIO will analyze potential programs of public funding and sources of private funding and potential investors at regional, national and European level for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects.</p> <p>2) MARG Members can update the analysis and include alternative sources for funding. A report on the funding sources will be kept</p>	P-BIO	MARG Members	Human Resources	31/03/2025	A report containing a catalogue with funding opportunities for circular bioeconomy initiatives and Hub continuity.	Not enough data available / No viable funding sources for HUB continuity	Ask for the input of MARG Members. Catalogue will be regularly updated.

D2.1. Regional case studies

			open for updates throughout the project							
5	BioINSouth HUB mission and vision	Agreement of the BioINSouth HUB for Centro Region mission and vision	1) P-BIO will present a predetermined vision and mission for the Bioeconomy Hub 2) Both the mission and the vision will be discussed and updated with the feedback from MARG members	P-BIO	MARG	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Agreed definition of the mission and vision of the BioINSouth HUB	Difficulty in reaching an agreement	Discussion based on some initial draft information, to guide it and further commitment to a shared version that reflects the “vision” of all stakeholders.
6	Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus	Pre-identification of the most relevant areas of action of the BioINSouth Hub in the Centro region.	1) P-BIO will present a pre-version of primary areas of focus (supported by a questionnaire) developed by BioINSouth. 2) Discussion among the MARG Members and definition of areas of focus (may	P-BIO	MARG	Human Resources	13/03/2025	Agreed definition of primary areas of focus for the BioINSouth HUB	Low feedback / Difficulties in reaching an agreement	Discussion based on questionnaire answers and further discussion until reach an agreement with all MARG Members.

D2.1. Regional case studies

			change during the project course).							
7	Regional stakeholder engagement	Engagement of significant part of the relevant regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix to join the BioINSouth HUB in Centro Region.	1) Constant feedback from the MARG members of relevant stakeholders to be included in the HUB 2) Word of mouth to join the Hub from P-BIO; MARG Members and further the already engaged Hub stakeholders	P-BIO	MARG Members / HUB member representatives	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Invitations to potential HUB members (minimum 15 entities)	Low engagement	Develop contacts with MARG Members for close contact with them. Organize bilateral meetings to explain the HUB, its role and its objective. MARG Members can at any time be challenged to develop further efforts to identify new members.
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth HUB Terms of Reference (ToR) and Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)	Development of templates for the BioINSouth HUB Centro Region including a presentation, terms of reference and preliminary activities definition. A MoU developed with feedback from the MARG Members will serve to formalize the HUB integration of the entity	1) P-BIO develop final draft documents (especially the MoU) after feedback and suggestions from MARG Members	P-BIO	MARG Members	Human Resources	31/03/2025	1 HUB Presentation 1 MoU agreed template	Low feedback / Difficulties in reaching an agreement	Discussion until reach an agreement with all MARG Members.

D2.1. Regional case studies

9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning	Preparation activities for the BioINSouth HUB KOM including date definition, event preparation actions, and meetings with potential HUB members.	1) Agreement of a suitable date and format with MARG members. 2) P-BIO will coordinate the event preparation. MARG members may be asked to support with some specific needs.	P-BIO	MARG Members	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Agreed date for the HUB KOM	Difficulties in the preparation of the event	Support from MARG Members
10	BioINSouth Centro Region HUB KOM	Establishing the BioINSouth HUB in Centro Region and is marked by the organisation of the KOM and the creation of a network of at least 15 stakeholders (MoU signed).	1) The establishment of the HUB (presentation of entities / founding members); 2) Communication plan of the activities related to the HUB and Working groups based on the priority areas of focus;	P-BIO	HUB Member representatives	Human Resources	30/04/2025	1 HUB KOM event Official launch for the BioINSouth Centro Region (min 15 entities)	Not reaching the minimum of 15 members	Engaging with more relevant stakeholders promoting bilateral meeting to explain the HUB. Ask for MARG members support on reaching more stakeholders

Satisfaction survey results:

The main results of the Satisfaction survey are presented here:

Organização
8 respostas

Relevância do tópico e conteúdo
8 respostas

- Excelente (5)
- Muito bom (4)
- Razoável (3)
- Fraco (2)
- Muito fraco (1)

Nível dos oradores (qualidade e clareza)
8 respostas

Participação e diálogo com o público
8 respostas

- Excelente (5)
- Muito bom (4)
- Razoável (3)
- Fraco (2)
- Muito fraco (1)

Local de realização do evento
8 respostas

Escolha do local / qualidade do almoço
8 respostas

- Excelente (5)
- Muito bom (4)
- Razoável (3)
- Fraco (2)
- Muito fraco (1)

Caso tenha qualquer comentário ou feedback sobre o evento e/ou o plano de trabalho a nível regional no âmbito do projeto BioINSouth, por favor deixe a sua contribuição abaixo

1 resposta

numa proxima reunião seria ideal ter tarefas específicas, momentos com WG ou atividades digitais para captação de brainstorming.

Figure 25: Centro Region MARG KOM Satisfaction Survey Results

In 8 responses, 62,5% of the participants classified the organization of the event as “excellent (5)” and 25% as “very good (4)”. Only one person (12,5%) classified it as “reasonable (3)”. In terms of Relevance of the topic and content 50% classified it as “Excellent” and 50% as “Very Good”.

In terms of the Level of the speakers (quality and clarity), 50% of the participants classified it as “excellent (5)” and 37.5% as “very good (4)”. In terms of Participation and dialogue with the audience, 37.5% classified it as “Excellent” and the remaining 62,5% as “Very Good”.

In terms of the Location and the Networking Luch (both location and quality), 87.5% of the participants classified it as “excellent (5)” and 12.5% as “very good (4)”.

As an additional comment one person stated “in a next meeting, it would be good to have specific tasks, moments with WG (“working groups”) or digital activities for brainstorming”.

Analyzing the satisfaction survey all together, we can conclude that the kick-off meeting fulfilled the objectives and people were pleased to attend. It will be good to reinforce the group to do active work to start building the Centro Region-PT bioeconomy Hub.

6.5 CYPRUS MARG KOM

6.5.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

BioINSouth Cyprus MARGs (Multi Actor Regional Groups) Kick-Off Meeting

Regional customisation:

A personalized invitation through e-mail to the event was sent to all MARGs members in Greek.

The local language (Greek) was used throughout both the presentation session and the workshop/discussion session, ensuring accessibility and engagement for participants. A dedicated short presentation was delivered on the bioeconomy landscape in Cyprus, providing relevant contextual insights.

The event was organized in an eco-friendly and sustainable manner, featuring vegetarian catering and avoiding paper printouts. Instead, digital screens at the venue were used to display banners, and tablets were employed during the co-design workshop to minimize environmental impact.

Agenda:

Friday, 14/03 10.00 – 13.00

10.00 – 10.20: Networking Coffee

10.20 – 11.00: Presentation (Part A)

Introduction to Bioeconomy

Introduction to BioINSouth

MARGs → aim, members role

Meet up of MARGs members – a few words each on background and relative experience

Presentation (Part B):

Bioeconomy in Cyprus

BioINSouth HUBs

Aim and objectives of today's meeting

11.00 – 12.30: Interactive workshop

Bioeconomy in Cyprus: Vision – Where we are, where do we want to go, steps needed

BioINSouth Cyprus HUB mission and vision

BioINSouth Cyprus HUB primary areas of focus

Stakeholder mapping for BioINSouth Cyprus HUB

Action plan for next steps

12.30 – 13.00: Light lunch

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: 14/03/2025

Host: Frederick University

Registration: Through email reply (invitation email is presented in Annex in Greek)

Venue: face-to-face (Kimera Hall, Nicosia)

Figure 26: a) Event venue, b) Presentation and discussion during event with MARGs members, c) Outdoor area of event venue used for networking, d) Pre-meeting discussions.

Required equipment, material, logistics:

- Laptop and large screen for presentation
- Tablets and large screen for co-creation workshop
- Two large screens for BioINSouth banner
- Frederick University’s pads, brochure, pens
- Coffee and light lunch catering (vegetarian)
- Signature sheet (included in Annex)

Figure 27: a) Frederick University's pads & pens, b) Frederick University's brochure, c) Large screen for BioInSouth banner, d) Laptop and large screen for presentation.

Registrations:

A total of 9 people (out of the ten MARGs members), either MARGs members or their representatives, were registered to the event, including 1 from the private sector, 4 from academia, 3 from the public sector and 1 from environmental NGO.

Table 14: Cyprus MARG KOM Registrations

Name	Gender	Entity	Position
Phoebe Vayanou	Female	Nature Conservation Unit, Frederick University	MARGs member (Research – Academia)
Evi Demetriou	Female	School of Engineering, Frederick University	MARGs/ HUBs coordinator (Research – Academia)
Kyriaki Koumenidou	Female	School of Engineering, Frederick University	Representative of MARG member (Paris Fokaides) (Research – Academia)
Marios Adamides	Male	Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment	MARGs member (Public Sector)
Kypros Antoniou	Male	Cyprus Chamber of Commerce & Industry	Representative of MARGs member (Andreas Andreou) (Industry)
Koula Michael	Female	Terra Cypria	MARGs member (NGO)
Savvas Maliotis	Male	Filagrogroun	MARGs member (Private Sector)
Panagiotis Dalias	Male	Agricultural Research Institute	MARGs member (Public Sector)
Natalia Georgiou	Female	Department of Environment	Representative of MARGs member (Theodoulos Mesimeris) (Public Sector)
Menelaos Stavrinides	Male	Cyprus University of Technology (CUT)	MARGs member (Research – Academia)

6.5.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants:

All the people who registered at the event participated. The participation list (signature sheet) is included as [Annex IX](#). 90% of the invited MARGs members (9 out of 10) participated in the event.

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop:

The event commenced with a 20-minute networking coffee, offering participants a relaxed environment to meet and connect with one another before diving into the workshop's activities.

Following the informal introductions, the workshop officially began with a presentation delivered by Phoebe Vayanou (included in [Annex IX](#) in Greek). To make the content more accessible and ensure clear communication, the presentation was conducted in Greek. Part A of the presentation introduced the concept of bioeconomy, as well as an overview of the BioINSouth project. The session also introduced the MARGs, outlining their purpose and the roles of their members.

Following that and to build a sense of community, MARGs members were invited to briefly share their backgrounds and relevant experience, as follows:

- **Evi Demetriou** from the School of Engineering of Frederick University. Background: research, academic on sustainable energy systems. Her role is MARGs/ HUBs coordinator.
- **Phoebe Vayanou** from the Nature Conservation Unit of Frederick University. Background on ecology, environmental impact assessment and sustainability.
- **Kyriaki Koumenidou** from Nature Conservation Unit of Frederick University. Background on research, academia on sustainable energy technologies and sustainability assessment of the built environment. Representative of MARG member Paris Fokaides.
- **Marios Adamides** from the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment. He is Head of Cabinet of the Minister of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment with background on agriculture, food chains, and local production.
- **Kypros Antoniou** from the Cyprus Chamber of Commerce & Industry, Representative of MARGs member Andreas Andreou. Background on Environmental policies, EU directives and legislation, circular economy.
- **Koula Michael** from environmental NGO Terra Cypria. Background on environmental awareness and sustainability (environmental education).
- **Savvas Maliotis**, Director of Filagroup. Background on rural economy, agricultural economics.
- **Panagiotis Dalias** from Agricultural Research Institute. Background on natural resources and environment.
- **Natalia Georgiou** from Department of Environment. Representative of MARGs member Theodoulos Mesimeris. Background on environment, sustainability, energy, waste.
- **Menelaos Stavriniades** from Cyprus University of Technology (CUT). Background on agricultural sciences, biotechnology and food science.

Then, Part B of the presentation, also delivered by Phoebe Vayanou, focused more locally, highlighting the state of the bioeconomy in Cyprus, the BioINSouth HUBs, and the aim and objectives of the day's meeting.

The event then transitioned into an interactive workshop (1,5-hour duration), facilitated by Evi Demetriou, Kyriaki Koumenidou and Phoebe Vayanou, where participants collaboratively explored several key topics:

- Envisioning the future of the bioeconomy in Cyprus
- Defining the mission and vision of the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB
- Identifying its primary focus areas
- Mapping key stakeholders
- Developing a preliminary action plan for next steps

The event concluded with a light lunch, providing another opportunity for informal discussion and networking.

The presentation (in Greek) can be found in [Annex IX](#), where BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop were presented.

Pictures from this session are the following:

Figure 28: Presentation and Discussion Sessions.

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

The national case study analysis was presented during the session ([Annex IX](#)).

During the discussion slot, Miro was used, where a main diagram ([Figure 29](#)) was already prepared that guided the discussion. This Diagram has various key points that were analyzed during the discussion.

Figure 29: Diagram used in Miro to guide the interactive/ discussion session.

The main points in relation to the Cyprus case study analysis, were the following:

- Bioeconomy is still in the early stages of development compared to other EU countries.
- Even MARG members are not fully aware of the bioeconomy concept.
- There is no bioeconomy strategy.
- There are various systemic problems in implementing a circular bioeconomy model, such as: lack of strategy/ policy and a key coordinating body, lack of organized supporting infrastructure, cultural attitudes (e.g. pay as you go is a scheme only being used now and still there is cultural resistance), lack of knowledge and monitoring systems (e.g. quantities of organic waste), no clear sources of funding.
- Additionally, due to the nature of Cyprus as an isolated island, it is important to ensure that supply material is enough for economically viable businesses.

Pictures from this session are the following:

Figure 30: Presentation of the regional/national case study analysis.

Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan:

As described in the session above, Miro was used, where a main diagram (Figure 29) was already prepared that guided the discussion and ideas and thoughts on the national working plan were noted in the Miro diagram.

The discussion was very fruitful in terms of participation and thoughts/ ideas sharing. Time did not allow to finalize the work plan, but it was concluded that a summary of the discussion points and conclusions will be sent to MARGs members in the days following the MARGs 1st meeting, in order to add and finalize the working plan.

The main points in relation to the Cyprus case study working plan, were the following:

Implementation targeted on a specific area/ topic → organic waste

Given the early development stage of the bioeconomy in Cyprus, it was discussed that it is more practical and achievable to focus on a specific area or topic rather than trying to address multiple sectors at once. A targeted approach allows for the development of focused implementation chains and best practices.

Among the various sectors, organic waste presents the most significant potential in terms of material supply, demand, and benefits.

Organic waste streams, such as food waste from tourism facilities, underutilized agricultural waste, and even invasive species like the *Lagocephalus sceleratus* (commonly caught and discarded by fishers), are more widely available in Cyprus. These diverse waste streams could be combined and processed into soil compost, a resource that is in high demand in the agricultural sector. Developing this approach would not only address waste management issues but also provide much-needed support to the island's agriculture by improving soil quality and sustainability.

To develop a circular bioeconomy chain focusing on organic waste needs to address various issues along the way such as logistics and organization of chain, ensure financial and environmental sustainability, stakeholders' involvement, participation and agreement, potential incentives to businesses, legal framework.

Refinement and Mapping of Potential Stakeholders

While some key stakeholders were identified during the discussion session, this area requires further exploration to ensure a comprehensive understanding of all relevant actors. A more thorough stakeholder mapping process is needed to establish a well-rounded HUB stakeholder group.

Awareness and educational campaigns on the value and potential of bioeconomy

Given the limited knowledge of bioeconomy, it is crucial to simultaneously focus on educational initiatives and capacity-building efforts. These efforts should aim to raise awareness about the principles and benefits of bioeconomy, while also promoting the potential market opportunities that could emerge from its implementation.

Next steps

- Circulate discussion points and conclusions to MARGs members in the days following the MARGs 1st meeting, to add to the working plan & stakeholders.
- HUBs KOM date - during July 2025.

Table 15: Working plan for the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members.

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Cyprus						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping	Identification of stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy in Cyprus to be involved in the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB	1) Frederick University will create a database with the list of potential stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy development based on its experience and participation in various initiatives. 2) Feedback and considerations from MARG's members will be requested.	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	31/03/2025 and will be updated by 30/04/2025 based on additional feedback by MARGs members	Database (excel file)	The database may not include all relevant stakeholders	Continue to map regional stakeholders and update the database
2	Regional needs assessment	Identification of regional needs and opportunities to develop specific actions.	1) Frederick University analyzed regional needs 2) The needs were introduced and jointly discussed with MARG's members 3) The needs will be continuously updated	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	31/03/2025	List of needs/opportunities	N/A	N/A
3	Analysis of pilot case studies	Definition of regional scenarios based on the information collected with the semi-structured interviews. Based on the answers, two scenarios will be projected.	1) Frederick University performed four semi-structured interviews to MARG's members 2) The information was analyzed in a comprehensive way 3) Results were shared to the MARG during the KOM,	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Presentation with the information collected from the semi-structured interviews	Potential discrepancies between MARGs members	Feedback during the KOM and jointly discussed

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Cyprus						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
			discussed and jointly validated							
4	Analysis of potential funding sources	Identification of the most relevant research and innovation opportunities	Analysis of national and international opportunities	Frederick University	MARG/HUB Cyprus	Human Resources	Continuous	List of potential funding sources	Underestimation of small, local funding sources	Continuous mapping
5	Agreement on BioINSouth HUB's Mission and Vision	Define Mission and Vision of BioINSouth Cyprus HUB	1) Frederick University presented during the MARG KOM the Vision and the Mission of the HUB 2) MARG's members were invited to provide comments/suggestions 3) Definition of Mission and Vision will be jointly validated	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	31/03/2025 Also to be further updated and validated in BioINSouth Cyprus HUB KOMM - July 2025	Final definition of the Mission and Vision of the HUB	This action does not involve big risks	N/A
6	Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus	Identification and selection of the most relevant areas of action of the BioINSouth Cyprus Hub.	1) MARGs members are asked to answer the questionnaire (QR code) during the KOM	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	14/03/2025	Answers from MARG members	This action does not involve big risks	N/A

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Cyprus						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
7	Regional stakeholder engagement	Engage relevant regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix in the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB.	1) Starting from the stakeholders present in the database, think about two rounds of invitations 2) Define the necessary documents for the engagement phase (e.g. membership form validated during the KOM)	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	30/05/2025	Minimum 15 to 30 stakeholders involved	Involve a minimum of 15 stakeholders by the deadline	Start involving after the MARG KOM and send reminders
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU	Develop templates for the engagement of local stakeholders in BioINSouth Cyprus HUB.	1) Development of the draft documents 2) Validation from MARG members	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	30/04/2025	Final regulatory and membership form	This action does not involve big risks	N/A
9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning	Organize the KOM of Cyprus HUB (date, logistics, invitations and agenda of the day)	1) Identify the date based on the availability of the room, Frederick team and MARG members 2) Organize the co-creation workshop including "state of the play"	Frederick University	MARG Cyprus	Human Resources	30/06/2025	Agreed date (17 or 18 of July)	This action does not involve big risks	N/A
10	MoU signature and HUB establishment	Establish the BioINSouth Cyprus HUB	1) Engage stakeholders; 2) Formal establishment during the HUB KOM, based on the formal signatures received.	Frederick University	MARG/ HUB Cyprus	Human Resources	30/05/2025	1 MoU / HUB member >= 15 members	Involve a minimum of 15 stakeholderS by the deadline	Be comprehensive in the engagement phase by explaining the

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Cyprus						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
			3) Start planning the activities of the HUB.							benefits of joining the HUB

Satisfaction survey results

The satisfaction survey template is presented in the [Annex IX](#).

It was completed electronically *through the website* <https://www.surveymonkey.com>.

The results are the following:

- Organization – 5 Excellent (9 out of 9)
- Relevance of the topic and content - 5 Excellent (9 out of 9)
- Level of the speakers - 5 Excellent (9 out of 9)
- Participation and dialogue with the audience - 5 Excellent (9 out of 9)
- Venue and catering - 5 Excellent (9 out of 9)

Image 31: Workshop evaluation based on satisfaction survey.

6.6 Nouvelle Aquitaine MARG KOM

6.6.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

“Kick-Off du COPIL BioINSouth”

Regional customization:

French was used to facilitate discussions. Most of the attendees were directors, ensuring a broad and strategic perspective on the discussions. The participation of a regional representative and institutional stakeholders was also crucial in aligning our conversations with existing policies and ongoing initiatives.

Agenda:

9.00 - 9.30: Welcome Coffee

9.30 - 9.40: Introduction to the BioINSouth project and workshop objectives

9.45 - 10.00: Presentation of the MARG concept and associated objectives

- Definition of MARG and objectives.
- Presentation of the state of the bioeconomy in New Aquitaine, including the responses to the semi-structured interviews conducted.

Open discussion.

10.00 - 10.15: Coffee break

10.15 - 11.50: Collaborative workshop on the design and implementation of the New Aquitaine Hub for bioeconomy.

- Co-construction of the roadmap: validation of the Hub's objectives and strategic priorities

11:50 - 12:00: Closure of the WG and conclusions

See [Annex X](#).

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: 27/03/2025

Host: Bordeaux Sciences Agro, hosting Agri Sud-Ouest Innovation (cluster partner)

Registration: Online

Venue: face-to-face

Figure 32: Meeting room of the MARG KOM.

Image 33: Official photo of MARG members presents at the KOM. *

* From left to right: Elodie Lacassagne (ACD), Cédric Cabanes (Un Autre Monde), Yoann Monget (Ademe), Laurent Augier (ASOI), Philippe Sommer (La Coopération Agricole), Arnaud Sergent (INRAE), Christophe Magro (CANOE), Olivier Laviolle (INRAE), Eva Mametz (ASOI)

Required equipment, material, logistics:

For the workshop, the equipment used consisted only of an overhead projector for the PowerPoint presentation and Post It notes for the collaborative activity. The agenda was sent to all participants beforehand.

Registrations:

A total of 17 people were registered to the event, including 7 from the private sector, 4 from academia and 6 from policy makers and other institutions (as consumers organizations).

The registration list:

Private Sector

- Philippe SOMMER, CEO, La Coopération Agricole Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Elodie LACASSAGNE, Innovation Manager, ACD Aquitaine Chimie Durable (Female)
- Frédéric BATAILLE, General Delegate, ACD Aquitaine Chimie Durable (Male)
- Eva MAMETZ, EU Project Manager, ASOI (Female)
- Laurent AUGIER, Director, ASOI (Male)
- Nicolas NGUYEN THEN, EU Director, ASOI (Male)
- Marc VINCENT, ex-CEO, Xylofutur (Male)

Academia

- Christophe MAGRO, CEO, CANOE Platform (Male)
- Olivier LAVIALLE, President, INRAE Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Arnaud SERGENT, Research Fellow (Forest Policy), INRAE Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Jean-David LEAO, Director, ITERG (Male)

Local Government

- Fabienne GRANDCHAMPS, Chemistry and Materials Project Manager, Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region (Female)
- Yoann MONGET, In Charge of Methanisation, Food and Agriculture, ADEME Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Luc SERVANT, CEO, Chamber of Agriculture of Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Marina SALLE, Project Manager, Chamber of Agriculture of Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Female)

Civil Society

- Cédric CABANES, Holding Un Autre Monde (Male)
- Yvette THOMAS, Former Farmer (Female)

6.6.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

A total of 10 people attended the meeting corresponding to a participation rate of 60%, and with 30% of whom were women. It included 4 people from the private sector, 3 from academia and 3 from policy makers and other institutions (as consumers organizations).

List of attendees:

Private Sector

- Philippe SOMMER, CEO, La Coopération Agricole Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Elodie LACASSAGNE, Innovation Manager, ACD Aquitaine Chimie Durable (Female)
- Eva MAMETZ, EU Project Manager, ASOI (Female)
- Laurent AUGIER, Director, ASOI (Male)

Academia

- Christophe MAGRO, CEO, CANOE Platform (Male)
- Olivier LAVIALLE, President, INRAE Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)
- Arnaud SERGENT, Research Fellow (Forest Policy), INRAE Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)

Local Government

- Fabienne GRANDCHAMPS, Chemistry and Materials Project Manager, Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region (Female)
- Yoann MONGET, In Charge of Methanisation, Food and Agriculture, ADEME Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Male)

Civil Society

- Cédric CABANES, Holding Un Autre Monde (Male)

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop

The BioINSouth project was presented to the audience, along with its objectives and the other partners. The role of the MARG was also outlined, including what is expected of its members:

- Co-creation sessions for:
 - The implementation of the BioINSouth regional HUB and the execution of a dedicated action plan.
 - The development of a regional case study based on information about the bioeconomy sector and the policy landscape.
- Forums for the exchange of good practice within and between BioINSouth HUBs, promoting capacity building.
- Interaction on an ad-hoc basis if deemed necessary and depends on the availability of MARG members.

See [Annex X](#).

Results/evidences from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis

The discussion focused on structuring the bioeconomy sector in Nouvelle-Aquitaine, leveraging stakeholder collaboration and strategic policy alignment. Tools, including regional bioeconomy diagnostics, stakeholder mapping, and the integration of national strategies were employed.

The discussion on biomass in Nouvelle-Aquitaine focused on its availability, mobilization, and the environmental constraints that may impact its future use. Participants evaluated the current biomass supply and acknowledged the solid planning already established for its utilization in the energy sector. A key question that was raised was how to sustainably mobilize additional biomass while maintaining a balance across different industries. Climate-related challenges such as drought, diseases, and water shortages were identified as major threats to biomass availability, highlighting the need for agricultural and forestry systems to adapt over the next 5 to 10 years. In this context, ensuring not only sufficient biomass quantity but also its quality is crucial to preserving the added value of bio-based industries.

The discussion also addressed the structuring of biomass-related value chains and the need for a clear mapping of key stakeholders. Additionally, the conversation differentiated between **organic biomass** (such as agricultural waste, bio-waste, and algae) and **lignocellulosic biomass** (such as timber, industrial wood, and non-forest biomass like vineyards and hedgerows). The overarching goal is to manage these resources efficiently and sustainably while anticipating the challenges posed by climate change and evolving bioeconomy strategies.

The next steps include completing the regional diagnostics, broadening stakeholder engagement, and further refining the mapping process.

See [Annex X](#).

Results/evidences from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan

Image 34: Regional stakeholder mapping workshop

Image 35: Overview of the mapping.

As part of the co-creation of an action plan for the Bioeconomy Hub in Nouvelle-Aquitaine, a collaborative workshop was organized to begin the process of mapping key stakeholders to be included in this initiative. During this brainstorming session, participants identified and categorized stakeholders into three main categories: **primary production, transformation, and market**. These categories were based on the types of structures involved, such as cooperatives, businesses, research institutions, and other relevant organizations across various sectors like agriculture, forestry, chemistry, health, and others.

The primary goal of this workshop was to bring together actors from bioeconomy to discuss the challenges and opportunities within each sector, particularly in the context of climate change and the potential reduction of available biomass in the future. By sharing insights, the aim is to plan the different coming activities of the HUB for 2025. An initial version of the action plan will be prepared for a second meeting in July, and will be further refined after validation with MARG members and HUB stakeholders during the meeting on 23 July.

Additionally, the workshop also revisited previous work done in the region, reviewing existing studies and analyses to build on these efforts in preparing for upcoming sessions. This included reviewing regional bioeconomy diagnostics and aligning with national strategies.

The next meeting is scheduled for early July, where the workshop will be combined with a session involving the Bioeconomy Hub stakeholders, as well as members of the MARG.

Furthermore, the definition of the Bioeconomy Hub was revisited during the session. Its primary objective is to bring together key stakeholders in Nouvelle-Aquitaine's bioeconomy sector, to accelerate the implementation of a strategic plan for regional bioeconomy development.

See [Annex X](#).

Satisfaction survey results

At the end of the meeting, ASOI collected participants' feedback, who expressed their satisfaction with both the organization and the high level of expertise among attendees. The topics and themes addressed were well received and met the expectations of all participants. A more detailed satisfaction questionnaire will be distributed during future sessions to better identify the strengths of these discussions and any potential areas for improvement.

6.7 Peloponnese MARG KOM

6.7.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

1st KOM of MARGs in Peloponnese – Greece

“Do not leave Peloponnese behind”

Regional customisation:

During the event, the local language (Greek) was used. The agenda was tailored to regional needs, and additional stakeholders from other regions were invited to share their experiences, ideas, and perspectives. Special attention was given to including young individuals without prior experience, to introduce them to the concept and help pave the way for their future professional careers

Agenda:

- Presentation of BioINSouth objectives
- Stakeholder presentations from Peloponnese, North Greece, Crete
- Presentation of relevant running projects
- Discussion and concluding remarks

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: March 21st, 2025. Peloponnese – Greece, 16:00h-18:30h

Host: National and Kapodistrian University of Athens – RI Bio3

Registration: via email (see [Annex XI](#)).

Venue: online.

Webinar meeting⁷

Organized by:

- Prof. Dr. Konstantinos Vorgias
- Assist. Prof. Dr Ieronymos Zoidakis

⁷ <https://uoa.webex.com/meet/cvorgias>

- Dr Aikaterini Stefi
- Dr. Charis Makri

Required equipment, material, logistics:

Exclusively personal computers were required.

Registrations:

Registration was conducted through direct email.

A total of 21 people registered for the KOM including 8 from the Academia, 2 from Public Administration, 9 from Private Sector, 2 from Civil Society.

Table 16: Peloponnese MARG KOM Registrations

	Name	Entity	Gender
1	Prof. Dr. Konstantinos Vorgias	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)	Male
2	Assoc. Prof. N. Monokrousos	International Hellenic University	Male
3	Dr. Yiannis Fallas	CLUBE	Male
4	Elena Anthis	ANTHIS SA	Female
5	Maria Andriellou	Greek Bioeconomy Council	Female
6	Prof. Dr. E. Topakas	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	Male
7	Nadia Vougogiannopoulou	PNO Innovation, Greece	Female
8	Christina Gardikioti	Founder Meraki People	Female
9	Nikos Damatis	Hellabiom	Male
10	Nasos Makios	KLIMIS	Male
11	Prof F. Ververiidis	Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU)	Male
12	Aggelika Mela	Consultant Epidavros Municipality	Female
13	Popi Sourmaidou	Joint Undertaking (SCE) Speira Earth Speira	Female
14	Dr Aikaterini Stefi	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA-RIBio3)	Female
15	Charis Makri	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA-RIBio3)	Female
16	Prof. K. Marinakos	Vice Pres. Council of Development and Innovation, Peloponnese District	Male
17	Assist. Prof. Ieronymos Zoidakis	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Male

18	Alexios Pantelias	AlexPant	Male
19	Vasilis Stenos	Solmeya	Male
20	Iakovos Delioglanis	FOCUS Strategic Thinking Consultants PC	Male
21	Panagiotis Georgiou	BioINSouth partner Cyprus	Male

6.7.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

A total of 15 people attended the KOM including: 6 from the Academia, 2 from Public Administration, 5 from Private Sector, 2 from Civil Society.

Table 17: Peloponnese MARG KOM Participants

	Name	Entity	Gender
1	Prof. Dr. Konstantinos Vorgias	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA-RIBio3)	Male
2	Assoc. Prof. Nikolaos Monokrousos	Professor at the Hellenic University and Director of the Master: Bioeconomy and Law	Male
3	Charis Makri	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA-RIBio3)	Female
4	Elena Anthis	CEO of ANTHIS SA	Female
5	Maria Andriellou	General Director of the Greek Bioeconomy Council	Female
6	Evangelos Topakas	Professor of Biotechnology at the National Technical University-Athens	Male
7	Nadia Vougogiannopoulou	BioINSouth D&C partner Innovation Consultant	Female
8	Christina Gardikioti	Meraki People Founder	Female
9	Nikos Damatis	General Secretary of Hellabiom	Male
10	Nasos Makios	CEO-KLIMIS	Male
11	Filippos Ververidis	Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU)	Male
12	Aggelika Mela	Consultant Epidavros Municipality	Female
13	Popi Sourmaidou	Joint Undertaking (SCE) Speira Earth Speira	Female
14	Dr Aikaterini Stefi	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA-RIBio3)	Female
15	Prof. K. Marinakos	Vice Pres. Council of Development and Innovation, Peloponnese Dinstric	Male

D2.1. Regional case studies

Males 8/16 (50%) and Females 8/16 (50%)

Results/evidences from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop:

BioINSouth
Supporting Regional Environmental Sustainability Assessment for the BioBased Sectors to Improve Innovation, Industries, and Inclusivity in South Europe

1st KOM of MARGs in Peloponnese
"Do not leave Peloponnese behind"

March 21st, 2025,
Peloponnese Greece, 16:00h-18:30h

Webinar meeting:
<https://vms.webex.com/jmeet/cvooxlas>

The objectives

Stakeholder engagement, guidelines, digital tools, and SSbD solutions towards the adoption of innovative methodologies for increased regional competitiveness, innovation capacity, fair & effective EU Green transition

The partnership

Partner	Country	Role
Italian circular bioeconomy cluster - SPING	Italy	Coordinator - Campania HUB coordinator
University of Naples Federico II - UNINA	Italy	Bio-economy modeling, artificial effects on ecosystems
University of Milan Bicocca - UNIBIC	Italy	Address drivers for biodiversity decline, biodiversity valuation
Technological Corporation of Andalusia - CIA	Spain	Andalusia HUB coordinator
Frederick University - FIU	Cyprus	Cyprus HUB coordinator
West Industry Association of Andalus - ASIRCA	Spain	Andalus HUB coordinator
Paraguay's Biotechnology Industry Organization - F.BIO	Paraguay	Centro HUB coordinator
BIOBASE HUB CR - BIOBASE	Costa Rica	Network mobilization of RTOs and policymakers
PNIO Innovation Greece - PNIO	Greece	Dissemination, communication, exploitation
Innovation Engineering - IMEK	Italy	Development of digital tools
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens - NKA	Greece	Peloponnese HUB coordinator
Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia - ACS	Slovenia	Slovenia HUB coordinator
AGRI EUB - GREAT INNOVATION - AGO	France	Nouvelle-Aquitaine HUB coordinator
Leitat Technological Center - LEITAT	Spain	ICA and SSbD assessment
Scientific and technological research council of Turkey - TÜBİTAK MAM	Turkey	Replication region

BioINSouth regional concept

Establishment of 8 regional HUBs in South Europe

- LEITAT, UNINA, UNIBIC, INNEN → technical expertise in environmental assessment
- BIOBASE HUB CR → management expertise
- TÜBİTAK → candidate replication region

Figure 36: Presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives.

The main objectives of the session were:

- Presentation of BioINSouth objectives
- Stakeholder presentations from Peloponnese, North Greece, Crete
- Presentation of relevant running projects
- Discussion and concluding remarks

Figure 37: Part of the presentation of Nasos Makios (KLIMIS) (left) and the platform of the Clube presented by Dr. Y. Fallas (right)

Figure 38: Part of the presentation of Maria Andriellou (GBC) (left) and the INDBioCAT project presented by Prof. Dr. E. Topakas (NTU) (right).

Figure 39: Part of the presentation of Nikos Damatis (Hellabiom) (left) and the activities of the Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU) presented by Prof. Dr. F. Ververidis (HMU) (right).

Figure 40: Presentation of the Business Plan of the AIM-HQ OIL project (left) and the Joint European master's degree (AIM-OPTIMOIL) between HMU-GR, ES-UJAEN and IT-UNIBAS, both presented by Prof. Dr. F. Ververidis (HMU) (right).

Results/evidence from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

The discussion was carried out in 2 stages.

1. Following each presentation, multiple stakeholders engaged with the speakers by asking questions.
2. The HUB coordinator compiled the main questions and presented them during the open discussion slot.

Include the final version of the working plan for the BioINSouth HUBs establishment agreed with the MARGs.

- The Peloponnese has a low ranking in the list of implications of SDGs and requires support to improve its position.
- Peloponnese show a limited record in acquiring EU funding and this record is solely obtained by the Academic entities.
- Public awareness is quite limited.
- The Peloponnese has a very extended coastal line which is under strong erosion and measures must be taken. This coastal line of Peloponnese provides ideal conditions for fish farming.
- The Peloponnese, due to extended virgin mountains, provides an ideal biodiversity depository.
- The Peloponnese have extended unused-marginal land.

- Agricultural properties are divided into small areas and therefore are not sustainable.
- No bioeconomy strategy or action plan on Circular Bioeconomy.
- A specific strategic plan exists under the RIS3, strongly focused on energy and pharmaceutical industries.
- There are limited university modules available at the graduate and master's levels. There is strong interest from the tourism sector in getting involved, due to the presence of key archaeological hotspots such as Olympia, Epidaurus, Mystras, and Monemvasia. However, these sites are not currently reflected in the bioeconomy communication strategy.

D2.1. Regional case studies

Table 18: Working plan for the BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB establishment agreed with the MARG members

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
1	Regional stakeholder mapping	Identification of stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy in Peloponnese to be involved in the BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB	1) NKUA will create a database with the list of potential stakeholders active in circular bioeconomy development based on its experience and participation in various initiatives. 2) NKUA and considerations from MARG's members will be requested.	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	31/03/2025 and will be updated by 30/04/2025 based on additional feedback by MARGs members	Database (excel file)	The database may not include all relevant stakeholders, particularly from the primary production sector.	A personal campaign is running to detect, meet and persuade regional stakeholders and update the database. Until now is successful, however is time consuming.
2	Regional needs assessment	Identification of regional needs and opportunities to	1) NKUA analyzed regional needs 2) The needs were introduced and jointly	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	31/03/2025	List of needs/opportunities	The stakeholders are partially informed and	By personal contact the situation is changing.

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
		develop specific actions.	discussed with MARG's members 3) The needs will be continuously updated						show lack of trust.	The local authorities are completely fixed to energy and water problems.
3	Analysis of pilot case studies	Definition of regional scenarios based on the information collected with the semi-structured interviews. Based on the answers, two scenarios will be projected.	1) NKUA performed 19 semi-structured interviews with MARG's members 2) The information was analyzed in a comprehensive way 3) Results were shared to the MARG during the KOM, discussed and jointly validated	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	31/03/2025	Presentation with the information collected from the semi-structured interviews	Potential discrepancies between MARGs members	Feedback during the KOM and jointly discussed
4	Analysis of potential funding sources	Identification of the most relevant research and	Analysis of national and international opportunities	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	Continuous	List of potential funding sources.	The funding sources are completely linked to Horizon	Continuous mapping and creation of groups of

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
		innovation opportunities							projects. National funding is mainly focused on entrepreneurship and pharma industry	partners to set up new projects.
5	Agreement on BioINSouth HUB's Mission and Vision	Define Mission and Vision of BioINSouth Peloponnese	1) NKUA presented during the MARG KOM the Vision and the Mission of the HUB 2) MARG's members were invited to provide comments/suggestions 3) Definition of Mission and Vision will be jointly validated	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	31/03/2025 Also to be further updated and validated in BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB KOMM - July 2025	Final definition of the Mission and Vision of the HUB	This action does not involve big risks	Mission and vision must be compatible with other local HUBs to create a critical mass
6	Agreement on BioINSouth	Identification and selection of the most relevant areas of	1) MARGs members are discussed during the KOM MARGs	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	14/03/2025	Answers from MARG members	This action does not involve big risks	Continue searching for low volume,

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
	primary areas of focus	action of the BioINSouth Peloponnese Hub.								high impact case studies
7	Regional stakeholder engagement	Engage relevant regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix in the BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB.	1) Starting from the stakeholders present in the database, think about two rounds of invitations 2) Define the necessary documents for the engagement phase (e.g. membership form validated during the KOM)	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	30/05/2025	Minimum 15 to 30 stakeholders involved	No risks. More than 20 are available and the list is growing.	Keep in continuous contact.
8	Preparation of the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU	Develop templates for the engagement of local stakeholders in BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB.	1) Development of the draft documents 2) Validation from MARG members	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	30/04/2025	Final regulatory and membership form	This action does not involve big risks	N/A

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
9	HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning	Organize the KOM of Peloponnese HUB (date, logistics, invitations and agenda of the day)	1) Identify the date based on the availability of the MARG members (due to dispersion, Hybrid meeting is more suitable. 2) Organize the co-creation workshop including "state of the play"	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	30/06/2025	Agreed date (3 of July)	This action does not involve big risks.	The action is parallel with the 7 th International Summer School for Circular Economy and Sustainable Development, organized by several stakeholders. This measure increases visibility.
10	MoU signature and HUB establishment	Establish the BioINSouth Peloponnese HUB	1) Engage stakeholders; 2) Formal establishment during the HUB KOM, based on the formal signatures	NKUA	MARG Peloponnese	Human Resources	30/05/2025	1 MoU / HUB member Currently 20 members	Involve a minimum of 20 stakeholders by the deadline	Be comprehensive in the engagement

D2.1. Regional case studies

MAIN OBJECTIVE				Establishment of the BioINSouth HUB in Peloponnese						
Nº	ACTION	OBJECTIVES OF THE ACTION	STEPS OF THE ACTION	LEAD PARTNER	KEY REGIONAL PARTNERS	RESOURCES NEEDED	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS CRITERIA/KPI	POTENTIAL RISKS	CORRECTIVE MEASURES
			received. 3) Start planning the activities of the HUB.							phase by explaining the benefits of joining the HUB

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Figure 41: The picture of the attendees. 16 belong to the MARGs, 3 are from the organizing committee and 1 was an external invited Master student from the International Hellenic University.

Results/evidence from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan

A key moment of the event was the presentation on the establishment of the Greek Bioeconomy Council (GBC), a major milestone in the regional and national bioeconomy agenda. The GBC, which will soon become a legal entity, already has over 25 registered members from academia and industry. Participants expressed strong interest in getting involved, and as a result, the Peloponnese HUB is expected to become part of the GBC. This is an important step to ensure its long-term sustainability.

There was also strong commitment from the region of Crete, which has already developed its own circular bioeconomy strategy and expressed solid support for the initiative.

Satisfaction survey results

Participants were very pleased and even surprised by the variety of topics presented and the depth of the presentations. There was a strong spirit of cooperation, and several bilateral discussions were initiated. We did not send out a questionnaire because the number of participants was manageable and people were fed up and do not really respond.

The survey was developed verbally during the final phase of the discussion. 15 responses show a very positive evaluation of the KoM, with all questions receiving a score between 4.0 and 5.0.

The results are the following:

- Organization – 5 Excellent (18 out of 15)
- Relevance of the topic and content - 5 Excellent (15 out of 15)
- Level of the speakers - 5 Excellent (14 out of 15)
- Participation and dialogue with the other participants - 5 Excellent (15 out of 16)
- New cooperations developed (2 out of 15)

6.8 Slovenia MARG KOM

6.8.1 MARG KOM Organization Phase

Official event title:

BIO(R)EVOLUTION: Where to Steer the National Bioeconomy?

The promotional poster for the event Bio(r)evolution: Where to Direct the National Bioeconomy? (Figure 42) taking place on March 6 at the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia (Dimičeva Street 13, Hall C). The poster features logos of projects and organizations such as CEE2ACT, BOOST BIOEAST, BioINSouth, BIOLOC, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food of the Republic of Slovenia, Anteja, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia – Association of the Chemical Industry, Circular Change, and the European Union as a funding partner.

Figure 42: Promotional poster for the event Bio(r)evolution: Where to Direct the National Bioeconomy?

Regional customization:

The language used to present was Slovenian. The event was entirely in Slovene, also the presentations and discussion were in national language to better include all the participants. Also, the LinkedIn post (before and after the event) were in Slovenian, published in the ACIS LinkedIn page. Except the posters attached to the wall during the event were in English.

Agenda:

Program

- 9.45–10.00 | Dobrodošlica ob kavi in registracija
- 10.00–10.10 | Pozdravni nagovor, aktivnosti za leto 2025 | **Alenka Dovč - Gospodarska Zbornica Slovenije - Združenje Kemijske Industrije, Ladeja Godina Košir - Circular Change in Miha Škrokov - Anteja ECG**
- 10.10–10.20 | Predstavitve svetovalnega odbora Stičišča | **Alenka Dovč - Gospodarska Zbornica Slovenije - Združenje Kemijske Industrije**
- 10.20–10.35 | Pogoji poslovanja (“Terms of Reference”) – podpis ToR Stičišča | **Marco Segovia Bifarini, Circular Change in Mario Plešej, Ministrstvo za kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in prehrano**
- 10.35–11.35 | Prvi del delavnice o oblikovanju nacionalnih smernic za biogospodarstvo in akcijskega načrta Slovenije - **Izvajalci: Ladeja Godina Košir in Marco Segovia Bifarini - Circular Change, Miha Škrokov - Anteja ECG**
- 11.35-11.45 | Coffee break
- 10.35–13.15 | Drugi del delavnice o oblikovanju nacionalnih smernic za biogospodarstvo in akcijskega načrta Slovenije - **Izvajalci: Ladeja Godina Košir in Marco Segovia Bifarini - Circular Change, Miha Škrokov - Anteja ECG**
- 13.15–13.25 | Priložnosti za Inovatorje v Biogospodarstvu. Projekt COPILOT: Kako izkoristiti vavčerje? | **Nina Meglič, SRIP Krožno Gospodarstvo**
- 13.25–14.00 | Kosilo in mreženje

Lokacija

Gospodarska Zbornica Slovenije - [Dimičeva 13, Ljubljana, 1. nadstropje, dvorana C.](#)

Figure 43: Slovenia MARG KOM Agenda

Date, host, registration and venue:

Date: 6th of March 2025

Host – Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, ACIS

Registration:

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<https://si.bioloc.eu/2025/03/31/biorevolucija-kam-usmeriti-nacionalno-biogospodarstvo/>

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf54Dxkb7fcvBRignVRPoD0o64LNXI8i2WQ1K4fL5KYqNlKQQ/viewform?usp=sharing>

Venue: CCIS-ACIS, Dimičeva 13, Ljubljana

Figure 44: Highlights of the event, project presentations, and audience participation.

Required equipment, material, logistics:

PowerPoint presentation, computer, projector, projector screen. In addition, a BioINSouth posters translated into Slovene were put on the wall. A signature list was also prepared using the official BioINSouth template with logo. For two workshops carried out during the event, A2 paper pads and markers were provided for participants, brainstorming about action plan of the HUB and biobased activities for the next few years. Refreshment stations with food, water, and hot drinks were also provided. After the event, the participants received all the material shown during the event, a report was also sent to them.

Figure 45: Brainstorming session.

Registrations:

39 people were registered including MARG members from different sectors such as Academia/Research Institutions, Private Sector, Public Sector, Non-Governmental Organizations, Innovation and Business Support Organizations and Self-Employed Professionals. The event was composed of MARG Kick Off and two additional workshops prepared in collaboration with other EU projects running in Slovenia. Below, there is a list of registered people.

Table 19: Slovenia MARG KOM Registrations

	Name and Surname	Gender	Entity	Position
1	Barbara Simonič	F	/	Associate Professor
2	Ivan Knechtl	M	Aetheria	Consultant
3	Mateja Novak	F	Anteja ECG d.o.o.	Project Manager
4	Petra Marinko	F	Avenia M - Non Tox Uni Kum	Chief Executive Officer
5	Matej Fatur	M	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Researcher
6	Janja Rudolf	F	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Associate Researcher
7	Bojana Bogovič Matijašič	F	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Senior Research Fellow
8	Helena Cvenkel	F	BSC KRANJ	Director of Research and Development
9	doc.dr. Sandra Damijan	F	Faculty of Economics, UL	Researcher
10	Luka Klemen	M	ETRI community	Chief Communications Officer
11	Lenka Puh	F	ETRI community	Idea manager
12	Bogo Seme	M	HEDONI d.o.o.	Director
13	David Ravnjak	M	Pulp and Paper Institute	Director
14	Petra Stražar Gatalo	F	National Institute of Chemistry	Independent Expert
15	Gasan Osojnik	M	National Institute of Chemistry	Scientific Associate
16	Katja Makovšek	F	National Institute of Chemistry	Postdoctoral Research Associate
17	Maja Čič	F	National Institute of Chemistry, DUBT Center	Researcher
18	Viktor Jejčič	M	<u>Agricultural Institute of Slovenia</u> , Department for Agricultural Engineering and Energy	Head of Department
19	Božidar Resnik	M	Municipal Utility Company Logatec	Director
20	Nina Durini	F	KOTO d.o.o.	Technical safety expert

21	Marija Čebular Zajec	F	Ministry of Economy, Tourism and Sport	Undersecretary
22	Katarina Krek Hudoklin	F	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food	Head of the Accreditation Department, Payment Agency
23	Mojmir Flisek	M	Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation	
24	Marjana Dermelj	F	Ministry of Public Administration	Secretary
25	Mario Plešej	M	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food	Senior Adviser
26	Klavdija Strmšek	F	Ministry of Environment, Climate and Energy	Senior Adviser
27	Dejan Mitrovic	M	Moree	Co-founder and Chief Product Officer
28	Matjaž Božič	M	Mycopor	Manager
29	Blaž Medja	M	Laško Union Brewery	Sustainability Manager
30	Darija Pavlovič	F	s.p. (Self-Employed)	
31	Majda Potokar	F	Technology Park Ljubljana	Project Manager
32	Milan Zrim	M	TVG Technologies - Institute	Senior Developer Project Lead
33	Luka Juvančič	M	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Associate Professor
34	Darja Demšar	F	Institute for Sustainable Development ISD	Project Manager
35	Irena Šimenko	F	Zenteh d.o.o.	Director, Environmental Project Manager
36	Alenka Dovč	F	ACIS	Project Manager
37	Miha Škrokov	M	Anteja ECG d.o.o.	Project Manager
38	Marco Segovia	M	Circular Change	Project Director and Circular Ecoomy Consultant
39	Ladeja Godina Košir	F	Circular Change	Executive Director

6.8.2 MARG KOM Results

Participants

A total of 30 people joined the event, 11 representatives of academia (research institutes, technology parc and faculties), 11 representatives of private sector or company representatives, 3 representatives

of civil society and 5 representatives of ministries. 78% of the MARG members invited attended (7 out of 9 members).

Table 20: Slovenia MARG KOM Participants

	Name and Surname	Gender	Entity	Position
1	Barbara Simonič	F	/ University of Ljubljana (UL) Faculty of Natural	Associate Professor
2	Ivan Knechtl	M	Aetheria	Consultant
3	Mateja Novak	F	Anteja ECG d.o.o.	Project Manager
4	Matej Fatur	M	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Researcher
5	Janja Rudolf	F	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Associate Researcher
6	Bojana Bogovič Matijašič	F	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Senior Research Fellow
7	Luka Klemen	M	ETRI community	Chief Communications Officer
8	Lenka Puh	F	ETRI community	Idea manager
9	David Ravnjak	M	Pulp and Paper Institute	Director
10	Petra Stražar Gatalo	F	National Institute of Chemistry	Independent Expert
11	Katja Makovšek	F	National Institute of Chemistry	Postdoctoral Research Associate
12	Maja Čič	F	National Institute of Chemistry, DUBT Center	Researcher
13	Marija Čebular Zajec	F	Ministry of Economy, Tourism and Sport	Undersecretary
14	Mojmir Flisek	M	Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation	Advisor at Higher Education sector
15	Marjana Dermelj	F	Ministry of Public Administration	Secretary
16	Mario Plešej	M	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food	Senior Adviser
17	Klavdija Strmšek	F	Ministry of Environment, Climate and Energy	Senior Adviser
18	Dejan Mitrovic	M	Moree	Co-founder and Chief Product Officer

19	Matjaž Božič	M	Mycopor	Manager
20	Blaž Medja	M	Laško Union Brewery	Sustainability Manager
21	Darija Pavlovič	F	s.p. (Self-Employed)	
22	Majda Potokar	F	Technology Park Ljubljana	Project Manager
23	Luka Juvančič	M	Biotechnical Faculty, UL	Associate Professor
24	Darja Demšar	F	Institute for Sustainable Development ISD	Project Manager
25	Irena Šimenko	F	Zenteh d.o.o.	Director, Environmental Project Manager
26	Alenka Dovč	F	ACIS	Project Manager
27	Miha Škrokov	M	Anteja ECG d.o.o.	Project Manager
28	Marco Segovia	M	Circular Change	Project Director and Circular Ecoomy Consultant
29	Ladeja Godina Košir	F	Circular Change	Executive Director
30	Jaka Kranjc	M	Ecologists Without Borders	Secretary General

Results/evidence from the introduction session: brief presentation of the BioINSouth project and main objectives of the workshop

The workshop began with a short introduction to the BioINSouth project, delivered by Alenka Dovč, evidence attached below (presentation is in [Annex XII](#)).

To make the content more accessible and ensure clear communication, the presentation was translated into Slovene.

The part of the MARG KOM event included:

- Introducing the members of the Slovenian MARG group – names, institutions and function.
- Sharing the insights and findings from the regional case study, based on conducted interviews, followed by discussion of the MARG members and other participants.
- Discussing the action plan for HUB activities in 2025 (Slovenia has already established a national bioeconomy HUB in October 2023).

These aims were previously shared with MARG participants via email.

Figure 46: Alenka Dovč presenting BioINSouth project, MARG members and tasks.

Results/evidence from the presentation of the regional/national case study analysis:

An overview of the Slovenian case study was shared with the MARG members through a PowerPoint presentation (see [Annex XII](#)) is also available in the project's shared folder. Conclusions can be found in the last slide of the presentation.

The presentation summarized key insights gathered from four interviews conducted with selected members of the MARG group who are actively involved in the Slovenian bioeconomy landscape. These participants were carefully chosen for their in-depth knowledge and strong regional understanding of the sector.

Given their distinct professional backgrounds, two different interview formats were applied to best capture relevant perspectives and information (3 interviewees filled out the format A and one format B).

The individuals interviewed were:

First name	Last name	Gender (Male/Female)	Stakeholder Category	Email	Organisation	Position	Sectors of Expertise
Luka	Juvančič	Male	Academic institutions	Luka.juvancic@bf.uni-lj.si	Biotechnical faculty - University of Ljubljana	professor	biotechnology, agriculture
Blaž	Likožar	Male	Academic institutions	Blaz.Likožar@ki.si	Chemical institute	researcher	chemistry
David	Ravnjak	Male	Academic institutions	david.ravnjak@icp-lj.si	Pulp and paper institute	researcher	pulp and paper
Nina	Meglič	Female	Private sector	nina.meglic@sgz.si	SRIP Circular economy	consultant	Circular and biobased economy

Table 21: MARG Slovenia members interviewed.

At the end of the presentation, the participants filled out the survey regarding the area of focus for the Slovenian bioeconomy HUB.

Figure 47: Participants filling out an online survey regarding area of focus of Slovenian bioeconomy HUB.

Results/evidence from the co-creation of the regional/national working plan:

During the second part of the event, the workplan for Slovenian bioeconomy HUB for the year 2025 took place. It should be noted that the Slovenian bioeconomy HUB was already established in October 2023. Since then, four major HUB events have been organized, each bringing together between 25 and 60 participants. The establishment of the HUB was a result of BIOLOC project (Horizon Europe), that is still running at Association of Chemical Industries of Slovenia. The HUB was created in collaboration with other projects, that include Slovenian partners from other institutions (CEE2ACT – Anteja ECG and BOOST4BIOEAST – Circular Change and Ministry of Agriculture of Slovenia).

Below, there is a table (Table 22) of all the activities that were discussed during the workshop. Relevant agreements and comments gathered during the event were:

Table 22: HUB activities for 2025, discussed during the workshop.

ACTION	COMMENTS
Regional stakeholder mapping	A detailed regional stakeholder mapping was prepared for the Horizon Europe project - CeleBIO, by ACIS. The document is available in the shared folder. The MARG will analyze this document to identify the key relevant stakeholders who could be potential actors for the Slovenian BE HUB.
Regional needs assessment Analysis of pilot case studies	It was agreed that regional/national needs assessment will be done by identifying the most promising sectors and industries with strong potential growth in the field of bioeconomy. It will also involve updating and evaluating the region's biomass resources to reflect current availability and usage. In addition, a comprehensive SWOT analysis was carried out during MARG workshop on different case studies – results are pasted below this table (*).
Analysis of potential funding sources	Within ACIS, a working group for sources of financing is active, of which a member is also a representative of BioINSouth project – the main task of this group is a constant ongoing review of potential programs of public funding and sources of private funding and potential investors at regional, national and European level for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects. The list of such financing will be constantly updated and shared with MARG members.

<p>Agreement on BioINSouth HUB's mission and vision Agreement on BioINSouth primary areas of focus Regional stakeholder engagement</p>	<p>A discussion regarding vision, mission, key stakeholders and areas of focus lead to a document below this table (**). Here is a short summary: MARG members highlighted key elements for establishing a bioeconomy hub in Slovenia. The hub should promote local biomass use, support high-value bio-based products, and act as a knowledge and advocacy platform. Priority sectors include agriculture, forestry, and bio-based industries, with strong emphasis on collaboration between research, industry, and local communities. SMEs should be supported through tailored services and financial incentives. MARG members suggested various organizational models and identified agroecology, food systems, bioenergy, and education as strategic focus areas for the Slovenian bioeconomy.</p>
<p>Preparation of the BioINSouth Regional HUB MoU</p>	<p>In course - the regional/national HUB MoU is being prepared with other partner institutions – HUB leaders, CEE2ACT and BOOST4BIOEAST. It was agreed that the MoU will be a part of ToR.</p>
<p>HUB's Kick-off Meeting Planning</p>	<p>The HUB was already established in October 2023. Next HUB event is planned on September 15th, 2025. The agenda will be shared with MARG members as soon as prepared.</p>
<p>Online/ in-person/ hybrid Kick-off Meeting (KoM)</p>	<p>Yes – 6th of March – in person.</p>
<p>MoU signature and HUB establishment</p>	<p>As said, HUB was already established, MoUs will be signed in September 2025, this was agreed between HUB leaders.</p>

(*) Insights from the 4th Workshop of the National Hub for Bioeconomy – SWOT analysis for case studies to be included in Action plan

General SWOT

Opportunities

- Connections of regions within Slovenia with the strategies
- Chitin/Chitosan from insects is an opportunity
- Invasive species like *Reynoutria Japonica* could be valorized to produce phenols and cellulose components or for biochar and biodiesel

D2.1. Regional case studies

- Pectin is still big and can be used as a gelling agent and can be extracted from the leftovers from plants
- Capturing CO₂ in fermentation processes
- Electrolysis of wastewater to extract H₂, Methane, ...

- New groundbreaking technologies are here
- These circular solutions can lower costs for the industry in the long run
- Opportunity to break into new markets with implementing circular tech

Threats

- Finances
- Low recognition of business models
- Regulation
- Too small market potential
- Large dispersion of sources
- Costs of logistics are a big threat
- Investments in these techs is large
- The largest threat: reticence of traditional investors/owners
- Geopolitical uncertainty
- Local policy is not flexible

Weaknesses

- Large dispersion of sources
- Lack of infrastructure
- Expensive processes
- Knowledge is not connected
- Time to develop an innovation
- Finding bio-solutions with a high-added value
- Lack of commitment of larger organisations to pilot projects
-

Strengths

- High added value
- Specialization
- Knowledge is high
- A good material flow inventory has been developed
- Resilience of organizations

Lignocellulosic value chain SWOT

Strengths

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D2.1. Regional case studies

- Most extensive raw material flow in Slovenia
- Lot of knowledge, TRL 3-6 is strong
- A strong pool of creative industry for added value

Weaknesses

- Limited access for new undertakings
- Fragmented ownership of forests
- Poor utilization of private forests
- Knowledge of new value chains at TRL 3–6 is available, but no equipment is currently in place
- Uncertainty in the ownership of leading processing companies
- Lack of financing in the early stages

Opportunities

- Proximity economy is essential - identifying and promoting local champions
- Sustainability commitments from companies (e.g. sustainable packaging)
- Eco-design
- Incentives for businesses to engage in R&D activities (machines, equipment...)

Threats

- Knowledge and expertise, especially in higher TRLs is lacking.
- Short-term pressures from the leading technologies like biogas
- Unresponsiveness of policy – delay in reaction to new trends

PYROLISIS SWOT

Strengths

- Pyrolysis is a viable option if you use inputs like wood biomass and DDGS from the wastewater treatment plants to produce heat, biochar and sequester the other Co₂

Weaknesses

- You need a constant source of biomass
- Reliance of farmers on subventions, consequently smaller interest for investments and innovation

Opportunities

- The investment does not have to be large
- The availability of tech and maturity is there

Threats

- There is less interest from large industry for biochar
- Contamination with dangerous substances like heavy metals

WHEY SWOT

Strengths

- Whey to proteins is a viable path, currently there is a large material stream of whey that could be utilized in Slovenia. Technologies to transform it are mature as well. Knowledge is there.

Weaknesses

- Potential lack of demand in end products
- Lack of a national long-term strategy for larger investments in this field
- Lack of inter-ministerial coordination for these topics
- Small market and material quantities in Slovenia. A big need to have an international value chain.

Opportunities

- There is a constant flow of whey throughout the year.
- High added value for chemical and pharma as well as food industry.

Threats

- Microbiological contamination with inadequate transport and storage
- Competition for the source is large

() SLOVENIAN BIOECONOMY HUB – VISION, MISSION, STAKEHOLDERS AND AREAS OF FOCUS**

Vision and Mission of the Hub

- The hub should promote expanded value chains within the bioeconomy, with a focus on cascading use of biomass and closing loops using locally sourced biomass.
- Its goal is to accelerate the commercialization of high value-added bio-based products.
- It would serve as a network for knowledge exchange, idea-sharing, and project collaboration, with an additional role in advocacy at both national and EU levels.
- The hub would act as a representative body, advocating for the interests of stakeholders in policy-making processes.

Key Sectors and Stakeholders

- Primary sectors: agriculture, forestry, water systems.
- Processing industries: food, wood processing, paper, pharmaceutical, textile, and construction industries.
- Emerging/hybrid sectors: green chemistry, bioenergy, ecosystem services valorization.

D2.1. Regional case studies

- Institutions involved: research centers, financial institutions, NGOs.

Collaboration Between Research Institutions and Industry

- Thematic cooperation: industry presents challenges, researchers provide solutions.
- Financial instruments are essential for supporting pilot projects and risk-related R&D.
- Knowledge exchange through workshops, showcasing best practices, and aligning industrial needs with technological solutions.

Involvement of Local Communities

- Cooperation with municipalities, development agencies, and agricultural cooperatives.
- Raising awareness about the benefits of bioeconomy and sharing international best practices.
- Engagement with NGOs and local action groups.

Collaboration with Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

- A tailored approach and customized services for SMEs.
- Opportunities for hub membership and networking via industry associations.
- Incentives and financial support mechanisms targeted at SMEs.

Organizational Structure of the Hub

- Suggested formats: interest association (GIZ), private institute, or SRIP-type network.
- Continuous engagement and transfer of good practices from abroad are considered crucial.

Priority Thematic Areas for Slovenia

MARG members identified the following focus areas as key to future development:

- Agroecology
- Food systems
- Forestry and food system integration
- Biomaterials
- Bioenergy
- Education
- Biorefineries

Satisfaction survey results

A satisfaction survey was sent out to participants; you can find the results below:

- Overall satisfaction with the workshops is very high: all measured dimensions (duration, participants, gender balance, content relevance, format) scored between 4.3 and 4.7 on a 5-point scale.
- The impact of the hub meetings on expanding professional networks is rated moderately high (average score 3.8).
- Opportunities to voice opinions were considered adequate by 60 % of respondents, with an additional 30 % indicating they were partially adequate.
- Communication with stakeholders - average score 4.0.
- Confidence in communication - average score 3.9.
- Knowledge of relevant bioeconomy challenges - average score 4.3.
- Intention to continue collaborating with stakeholders met through BioINSouth is high: 90 % “Yes”, 10 % “Not sure”.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D2.1, "Regional Case Studies," documents the activities undertaken within Task 2.2, "Organization of the multi-actor approach in case study regions," a key component of Work Package 2, "Development of the BioINSouth multi-actor approach framework."

Task 2.2 focused on establishing and initiating the multi-actor framework at the regional level, a step identified within the project structure as necessary to support the overall BioINSouth project objective of integrating ecological limits into bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps within Southern European regions.

The implementation of project activities, including the development of guidelines and digital tools for circular bio-based activities and environmental impact reduction at the regional level, needs the involvement of regional stakeholders. These stakeholders comprise policymakers, public authorities, private sector representatives, funding and financial entities, civil society, academic institutions, and research entities relevant to the regional context. The integration of their perspectives contributes to the development of multiactor approach implementable strategies, tailored to regional needs, which is a foundational principle addressed by the work initiated in Task 2.2 and documented in this deliverable.

The **BioINSouth project** structure includes the establishment of **eight regional HUBs in Southern European regions** (Campania - Italy, Andalusia and Asturias - Spain, Centro Region - Portugal, Nouvelle-Aquitaine - France, Peloponnese - Greece, Cyprus, and Slovenia) as a mechanism for catalyzing regional development. The effective operation of these HUBs depends on connecting with local and regional realities and mobilizing regional knowledge and commitment. Task 2.2 directly addressed this requirement by focusing on the practical organization of regional actors, specifically the **Multi-Actor Regional Groups (MARGs)**, to facilitate co-creation and co-validation activities tailored to the regional context, which are essential inputs for the subsequent development of the HUBs (BioINSouth WP3).

Organizing these MARGs and facilitating their early interactions, as detailed in Deliverable D2.1, represents a step towards building a foundation for mutual engagement at the regional level. This engagement is intended to support addressing potential barriers and identifying opportunities for circular bioeconomy within each specific region, thereby feeding into future project tasks. **The establishment and structure of the Multi-Actor Regional Groups (MARGs) and the initial regional insights were a primary outcome documented in Deliverable D2.1.**

The successful establishment of the Multi-Actor Regional Groups (MARGs), serving as the initial implementation phase of the multi-actor approach within the regional context of BioINSouth. These groups were designed within Task 2.1 to include representation from the quadruple helix within each of the eight pilot regions, comprising local governments, the business community (including SMEs), academic/research institutions, the private sector, and civil society. The specification for at least eight representatives per region, with minimum representation from each category of the quadruple helix, aimed to secure a diversity of perspectives considered necessary for understanding regional bioeconomy systems and ensuring regional relevance.

The formal establishment of all eight regional MARGs was completed by Month 6 (November 2024), as reported in D2.1, representing a milestone for Work package 2. **The MARGs involved a total of 92 members across the eight regions.** The MARGs stakeholder representation across the quadruple-helix was **academia (35%), private sector (32%), public administration (18%), and civil society (15%).**

Data collected within Task 2.1 indicate that **40 members are women, comprising 43% of the total membership**, which addresses gender balance considerations within the project structures at the regional level (women representation beyond 40%). Representation from diverse groups is considered to contribute to ensuring that project strategies and tools developed in subsequent tasks are relevant to different segments of the population and the regional bioeconomy ecosystem.

The role of the MARGs, as defined in the project framework, is a regional advisory body. It includes providing knowledge and strategic input to the BioINSouth Hub Coordinators, with the aim of aligning subsequent project results with regional stakeholder requirements and specific regional contexts. This function is presented as supporting the application of project outcomes at the local and regional levels.

The initial activities, particularly the **semi-structured interviews**, began to highlight the diverse stages of bioeconomy development across the target regions, with some regions indicating activity is still in preliminary or early stages. These activities also initiated the identification of biomass raw materials available at the regional level (including agrifood, forestry, urban, marine, lignocellulosic, and livestock sources) as a key factor for biorefinery and bioeconomy development, while also noting potential constraints to biomass utilization and mobilization (including those related to climate change impacts).

The planned engagement of the MARGs is detailed as extending throughout the project duration and beyond, with participation expected in co-creation, co-implementation, and co-monitoring activities related to HUB models within their respective regional areas. Specific contributions outlined for MARG members, as introduced during the initial interactions, include supporting collaboration, assisting in regional stakeholder analysis, participating in co-creation/validation sessions for regional HUB creation, supporting HUB network implementation according to regional needs, providing feedback on assessment and monitoring systems related to their regional implementation, contributing to benchmarking of regional best practices, and participating in regional policy recommendation development. Materials such as Terms of Reference (ToR), a Declaration of Acceptance (DoA), and email templates were developed within Task 2.1 to support the process of group creation and formalization across the regions. The framework established allows for the inclusion of additional members as the project progresses, intended to further enrich the knowledge base and representation within each region. The constitution and planned involvement of the MARGs are presented as components for connecting BioINSouth activities with specific regional contexts and informing project results based on regional needs.

The MARG Kick-Off Meetings (KOMs) represented a key activity within Task 2.2, serving as the initial interactive event for the established MARGs in each case study region. The organisation of these meetings was conducted by the regional HUB Coordinators, following a methodology developed as part of Task 2.2, designed by CTA to facilitate the achievement of specific objectives and participant interaction at the regional level.

D2.1. Regional case studies

The stated objectives for the KOMs, as documented in D2.1, included: introducing the BioINSouth project to MARG members and other relevant stakeholders, presenting the MARGs (their objectives, members, roles), sharing and validating preliminary results from regional analysis (derived from interviews and questionnaires) and conducting a co-creation session to develop a regional working plan for the local HUB, aligned with guidelines from WP3.

The preparation for the KOMs incorporated information gathered through semi-structured interviews conducted with MARG members. These interviews, structured with sections for technical and non-technical profiles, aimed to collect information on regional situations considered relevant to inform the development of regional case studies and growth scenarios under WP4. **A total of 35 interviews were conducted, with 49% female interviewees**, addressing gender balance considerations within this data collection process. The information from these interviews was utilized as content for the KOMs to support the discussion and validation of regional growth scenarios with the MARG members.

Discussions held during the KOMs, provided further insights into the diverse regional landscapes. Common barriers to bioeconomy development identified across multiple regions included regulatory and bureaucratic hurdles, economic and financing constraints, lack of awareness and knowledge gaps among stakeholders, and limitations in supporting infrastructure. Regional specificities were also highlighted, such as challenges related to island logistics, land division patterns, or specific environmental pressures like coastal erosion. Conversely, discussions identified key enablers and opportunities, including the potential of technological innovation, the necessity of favorable policy frameworks and strategic collaborations, the value of robust economic assessment models, and the identification of promising sectors or resources unique to certain regions (e.g., marine biomass valorization, leveraging biodiversity or archaeological sites). **The validation process during the KOMs generally confirmed these preliminary findings while also generating valuable reflections on the methodologies employed and the need for adaptable, region-specific approaches moving forward.**

The KOM methodology developed within Task 2.2 offered flexibility in the event format (with a preference for face-to-face). Regional coordinators managed the event organization, including agenda, invitations, dissemination, registration, and feedback collection via surveys, adapted to the regional context. The agenda structure included project introduction, discussion of regional analysis results, presentation of MARG and HUB concepts, and the working plan co-creation session for the regional HUB. This structure aimed to support interaction and output generation relevant to the regional context.

The BioINSouth project successfully convened its Multi-Actor Regional Group Kick-Off Meetings (MARG KOMs) in the eight Southern European regions. The KOMs successfully mobilised a total of **140 stakeholders registered and 120 attended**, yielding an exceptional attendance rate of approximately **86%**. **Gender balance was nearly achieved (48% men, 52% women)**, and **stakeholder representation across the quadruple-helix was academia (43%), private sector (31%), public administration (17%), and civil society (10%)**. This balanced composition ensured diverse perspectives during discussions of growth scenarios and co-creation exercises.

Table 23 shows all the data collected.

Table 23: KPIs by Region: Registration, Attendance and Stakeholder Composition.

Region	Registered	Attended	Academia	Private	Public	Civil Society	Men	Women
Andalusia	17	16	8	4	2	2	7	9
Asturias	11	10	2	5	2	1	2	8
Campania	13	18	10	5	2	1	11	7
Centro (Portugal)	13	12	7	2	2	1	6	6
Cyprus	9	9	4	1	3	1	5	4
Nouvelle-Aquitaine	17	10	3	4	2	1	7	3
Peloponnese	21	15	6	5	2	2	7	8
Slovenia	39	30	11	11	5	3	13	17
TOTAL	140	120	51	37	20	12	58	62

Figure 48 compares the number of registered participants versus actual attendees at the MARG Kick-Off Meetings, broken down by region. It shows an overall attendance rate of **86 %**.

Figure 48: Registrations vs. Attendance by Region

The stacked bar chart (Figure 49) displays the distribution of attendees according to the “quadruple helix” model (academia, private sector, public administration, and civil society).

Figure 49: Stakeholder Composition by Region

Following the successful implementation of the methodological framework outlined in Work Package 2 (WP2), all BioINSouth regions have completed the necessary preparatory steps. As a result, they are now well-positioned to advance toward the next phase: the creation of the BioINSouth HUBs and the formal establishment of the BioINSouth network.

BioINSouth Info Box

The BioINSouth project aims to support decision-makers to incorporate considerations of ecological limits into their regional bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps relevant to circular bio-based activities. We aim to develop guidelines and digital tools, considering the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) assessment framework, to support the adoption of innovative methodologies to assess environmental impacts in multiple industrial bio-based systems, increasing regional competitiveness and innovation capacity, and contributing to the EU fair & green transition.

Find out more:

Website: <https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/104361906/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@BioINSouth>

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